

**AN ASSESSMENT OF CULTURE OF ALCOHOL AND DRUG ABUSE AMONG
IMAN IBOM YOUTHS**

Moses Idongesit PETERS
BSC (Hon.) Uniuoyo, MSc Uniuoyo
20/PG/SS/SA/PHD/008

SEPTEMBER 2024

**AN ASSESSMENT OF CULTURE OF ALCOHOL AND DRUG ABUSE AMONG
IMAN IBOM YOUTHS**

Moses Idongesit PETERS
BSC (Hon.) Uniuyo, MSc Uniuyo
20/PG/SS/SA/PHD/008

A DOCTORAL THESIS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF SOCIOLOGY AND
ANTHROPOLOGY
FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

SUBMITTED TO

THE POSTGRADUATE SCHOOL, UNIVERSITY OF UYO, UYO, AKWA IBOM
STATE, NIGERIA, IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR
THE AWARD OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY (PHD) DEGREE IN
SOCIAL/CULTURAL ANTHROPOLOGY

SEPTEMBER 2024

DECLARATION

I, Moses Idongesit PETERS, hereby declare that this doctoral thesis entitled "An Assessment of Culture of Alcohol and Drug Abuse among Iman Ibom Youths in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria" was written by me and that it is the correct record of my own research work. It has not been presented for a degree in another institution. I will not present it, or cause it to be presented, for a degree in another institution. All sources of information have been appropriately acknowledged using references and other acceptable methods.

Signed
Moses Idongesit PETERS

CERTIFICATION

This thesis entitled "An Assessment of Culture of Alcohol and Drug Abuse among Iman Ibom Youths in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria" by Moses Idongesit PETERS (20/PG/SS/SA/PHD/008) meets the regulations governing the award of the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D) of the University of Uyo. The work has made an original contribution to knowledge. It should be submitted to the Postgraduate school for approval.

(a) Supervisor

Signature Date 18/10/2024
 Name Dr. Nsidiwe Akpan Ukor Rank SENIOR LECTURER
 Department/Faculty SOCIOLOGY, ANTHROPOLOGY / SOCIAL SCIENCES

(b) Internal Examiner

Signature Date OCTOBER 18, 2024
 Name INIUBONG ANSA Rank SENIOR LECTURER
 Department/Faculty GEOGRAPHY AND NATURAL RESOURCES
 MGT. / SOCIAL SCIENCES

(c) Head of Department and Chief Examiner

Signature Date 18/10/24
 Name Dr. Anetok S. Ukor Rank Associate Professor
 Department/Faculty Sociology & Anthropology / Social Sciences

(d) External Examiner

Signature Date 18/10/24
 Name Prof. Otu A. Eke Rank Professor
 Department/Institution Sociology / UNIPORT

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my father Idongesit who has been with me all through my academic journey.

.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am grateful to the Almighty God for His love and mercies upon my life throughout my academic study. My gratitude goes to my supervisor, Dr. Nsidibe A. Usoro for not only playing the role of a supervisor but that of an elder brother throughout this academic work. I am grateful for his patience and the time he gave to read through the work. For making constructive suggestions, and guidance throughout this academic work. My gratitude also goes to my Head of Department Dr. Aniefiok Ukommi, my able Post Graduate Programmes Co-ordinator Dr Mrs. Dorothy N. Ononokpono, and all my lecturers in the Department of Sociology and Anthropology at the University of Uyo; Prof. P. Essoh, Prof. D. Okon. Prof. A. Brown. Prof, N. Akpan, Prof. E. Ukpong, Prof. M. Ikoh, Prof. O. Udoh, Dr N. Wilson, Dr S. Okijie, Dr V. Ben, Dr S. Offong, Dr E. Okorie, Dr B. Essien, and other staff for their contributions in my academic progress this far, God bless you.

My sincere gratitude goes to my beloved wife, Pst. Mrs. Emediong Moses Idongesit and my children Best Moses Idongesit, Wonder Moses Idongesit and Prevail Moses Idongesit for their love, support and prayers throughout my academic journey. I appreciate the encouragement of my course mates, especially Senator Aniekan Bassey who played the role of a big brother and financial sponsor throughout my academic programme. Thank you all and God bless.

ABSTRACT

This fieldwork was undertaken to assess the culture of alcohol and drug abuse among Iman Ibom youths in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The researcher made use of Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Hirschi's Social Bonding Theory for theoretical framework. Exploratory research design was adopted by the researcher. The sample for this study were aged between 18 to 50 years and above, who were randomly selected through the big-net approach from the randomly selected village across the Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area. The researcher adopted the Fatterman's big-net approach for sample size which was limited to and not above 400 interviewees for the study. Socio-demographic data were presented and analysed using simple percentage. Findings of the study presented as natural occurring texts in form of excerpts, and were analysed thematically using discuss analyses method. Findings of the study revealed that Iman Ibom youths indulge in anti-social and anti-moral behaviours under the influence of alcohol and drug abuse. Iman Ibom youths continue in alcohol and substance abuse as a cycle, they tend to engage in criminal behaviours under the influence of alcohol and psychoactive substance abuse. Mkpomkparawa has been a cycle of alcohol and drug abuse among the Iman Ibom youths. This cycle has been a traditional code and pattern through which alcohol and drug abuse is preserved and transfer from one generation to the other. Among others, the researcher recommend legislation, advocacy and sensitization of the youth, stakeholders and the public on the danger of alcohol and other psychoactive substance abuse in the name of tradition especially on the health aspect of the youths

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER	TITLE	PAGE
	Cover Page	i
	Title Page	ii
	DECLARATION	iii
	CERTIFICATION	iv
	DEDICATION	v
	ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	vi
	ABSTRACT	vii
	TABLE OF CONTENTS	viii
	LIST OF TABLES	xi
	LIST OF APPENDICES	xiii
CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION		
1.1	Background to the Study	1
1.2	Statement of the Problem	4
1.3	Objectives of the Study	7
1.4	Research Questions	7
1.5	Significance of the Study	8
1.6	Scope of the Study	9
1.7	Definition of Terms	9
CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE		
2.1	Literature Review	11
2.1.1	Alcohol, Drug Abuse and Youth's Distorted Values	11
2.1.2	Culture of Alcohol and Drug Use and Formation of Cycle of Alcohol and Drug Abuse among Youths	14
2.1.3	Mkpomkparawa (Traditional Youths' Items) and Creation of Culture of Alcohol and Drug among Youths	19
2.1.4	Culture of Alcohol and Drug Use and Criminal Behaviour among Youths	22

2.2	Summary of Literature Review	26
2.3	Theoretical Framework	30
2.4	Summary	39

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1	Research Design	41
3.2	The Study Area	41
3.3	Population of the Study	44
3.4	Sample and Sampling Technique	44
3.5	Data Collection Technique	45
3.6	Procedure for Data Collection	46
3.7	Instrumentation	46
3.8	Validity of Instrument	47
3.9	Reliability of Research Instruments	47
3.10	Method for Data Analysis	47
3.11	Limitations of the Study	47
3.12	Ethical Issues	48

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1	Data Presentation and Analysis	49
4.2	Findings	51
4.3	Discussion of Findings	71

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1	Summary	76
5.2	Conclusions	78
5.3	Recommendations	79
5.4	Contributions to Knowledge	79
5.5	Suggestions for Further Studies	80
	REFERENCES	81

LIST OF MY EXPECTED PUBLICATIONS	88
APPENDICES	89

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE	TITLE	PAGE
4.1	Participants' Socio-demographics	49

LIST OF APPENDICES

APPENDIX	TITLE	PAGE
1:	TRANSMITTAL LETTER	89
2:	INTERVIEW SCHEDULE	90
3:	PICTORIAL PAGES FOR ETHNOGRAPHIC PHOTOGRAPHS	94

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Culture defines activities and influences behaviours of people who live within an ecological location. Culture has been explained in many perspectives in relation to human behaviour and capabilities to adapt to a given environment (Peters, 2019). Tylor (1871) as cited in Modo (2016) sees culture in the complex whole that includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs and any other capabilities and habits that must be acquired by man as a member of any society. Modo (2016) further in his explanation posits that culture in its characteristics is an integral system of learned behaviour and lay down patterns of the society. Culture explains that human behaviour is learned by members of society as part of adaptation's responsibility (Peters, 2019). Culture provides society with the inherited transmission code of conduct as both part and function of the total system of life of society (Usoro and EKong, 2016). Every culture has what is considered to be a morally accepted substance for consumption and use for many purposes. Culture to a large extent constitutes acceptable delicacies and drinks in all societies, and the use of any consumable substance in all societies is socially acceptable or rejected by the members of the society depending on the socio-cultural precepts in terms of values and norms (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017). Alcoholic beverages as drinks have been a very important aspect of the cultural practices of people for many years (McGovern, 2009).

Alcoholic beverages and other illicit substances have been part of the culture of humans globally, and this implies that there exists a culture of alcohol and illicit use among human groupings across the world. Cultural determinations of what constitutes acceptable foods and drinks create patterns of culture of the use and abuse of alcohol and drugs in all societies. Usoro *et al.*, (2015) opined that communities through cultural practices determine

what they consume as foods and drinks. Heath (2001) posits that culture plays a central role in creating what is expected of individuals concerning problems that may be encountered through the abuse of drugs and other substances. Substance abuse is found to be rooted in the culture of the people (Peters, 2020).

According to World Health Organization report, drugs including alcohol, marijuana, heroin and tobacco are consumed and abused by people today (Adetiloye, 2022). Adetiloye further posits that among the abused substances, alcohol is rated the highest in the world today. Drug abuse has become a threat to the world as it is found in almost every country of the world among youth between 18 – 35 years of age (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2016). According to Ekpenyong (2012), the Office of the United Nations on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) Report (2005) states that about 200 million of the world population which is about five per cent of the population of the world between the ages of 15 to 64 years either use or abuse psychoactive substances once in twelve months and fifteen million of the population more in the next year which shows a growing rate of drug use and abuse annually. The author further mentioned that over the years the abuse of psychoactive substances and alcohol in the world has increased in recent years. The evidence of this is in the availability of varieties of alcohol and drugs in the ever-expanding spectrum of socioeconomic situations of the consumers. This development is not unconnected with the major challenge which is the persistent distribution of these substances in the world (notably marijuana and heroin) with cocaine. In many countries in Asia and Europe, Opiates as a substance contribute to 62 per cent of treatments of drugs which has been sought by the people since 2003. A total of 3.3 to 4.1 per cent of the population of the world have admitted that they consume drugs and other psychoactive substances like opiates, which the most alarming one is the trend reported by the UNDCP Executive Director that young people at young ages are becoming addicted to these substances. For example; in Pakistan, those who started abuse of heroin use at 15-20 years of age has doubled to almost

24 per cent, and a survey in the Czech Republic showed that 37 per cent of new drug users were teenagers between 15 and 19 years old (Ekpenyong, 2012). Ekpenyong further reported that alcohol and drug abuse, like heroin abuse among the Egyptians have become a challenge of concern because almost 6 per cent of students from secondary schools have agreed to consuming drugs.

By 4000bc the use fermented beverages which generated to the production of alcohol drinks and many other drugs have been used for thousands of years and alcoholic beverages have been fermented from an array of plants and fruits since at least 4000bc, both wine and beer were first made at about the same time in what are now Iraq and Iran and some of the earliest references to the use of alcohol are found in ancient Sumerian clay tablets that contain recipes for the use of wine as a solvent for medications (Abbott and Chase, 2008). Alcoholic beverages were introduced in larger quantities during colonial times in most part of the America, at about the same time that some groups were fermenting alcoholic beverages, the Sumerians were cultivating the opium poppy, which they named "hul gil" the plant of joy (Abbott and Chase, 2008). The opium poppy was used for its medicinal properties among the people to relieve pain and diarrhea, and for its mental properties to provide sedation and euphoria which is presence in the United States, in the form of opium, it was noted among early Chinese immigrants, and later heroin was introduced to urban minority groups, such as blacks and Hispanics and these drugs today are abused by the people (Abbott and Chase, 2008).

Adolescent and youth form the age group whereby humans tend to acquire more human behaviours as part of their transition from childhood to adulthood in order to adapt to a given cultural environment (Peters, 2020). The youths are mostly venerable and greatly involve in the cultural peril of alcohol and psychoactive substance abuse. Youths have been at the centre of alcohol and drug abuse, and the most affected group in term of negative impacts and consequences (Peters, 2020). The cultural setting of Akwa Ibom people has

alcohol and drug use patterns through which acceptability of some illicit substances as traditional required items among the people exist for traditional rites and cultural rituals. The youths of Akwa Ibom State through these enculturation mediums have found morally acceptable boundaries created for them to use alcohol drinks and other drug related substances, and in most cases abuse them as forms of cultural practices. Most of the youths under the adverse results of these drugs and alcohol have been the substance induced state of addiction, engagement in deviant and violent behaviours, and some are now having mental health issues, coupled with few rehabilitation centres for drug addicts in Akwa Ibom State.

According to Rodda (2009), these youths who are not under parental control or guidance can develop tendencies to indulge in alcohol and substance abuse, which will influence deviant behaviours like rape, pick-pocketing, truancy, loitering, auto theft, and kidnapping. From this perspective, and considering that Nigeria is a culturally rich nation with multi-ethnic groups that socially accept various kinds of alcoholic drinks and drugs as part of their traditional rites and cultural festivities, a lot of research has been conducted on the impacts of alcohol and drug abuse on youths' development, their well-being, and crime. However, the influence of the cultural perspective that grants the legitimate right to drink alcohol and take drugs has been overlooked, representing a gap that this study aims to fill. Therefore, this work seeks to examine the impacts of the culture of alcohol and drug use among youths in the Iman Ibom Clan of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Alcohol and drug abuse is a global concern today with every country having its bit of challenge to confront (United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime, 2007; Lakhanpal and Agnihotri, 2007). Nigeria has grown from drug consuming to drug producing nation

(Weekly Trust, 2016), and the consuming patterns of drugs are in the rich cultural diversity of the nation which is practised with the acceptability of some illicit substances, thereby making the state of alcohol, drug abuse a case of concern in the nation within every cultural group or ethnicity. Among the youths of ethnic minority, alcohol and drug abuse is an important factor in ethnic identity (Zapolski *et al.*, 2017). This can provide the moral license for abuse of alcohol and drugs.

Culture and drug abuse have been synonymous from pre-colonial Nigeria. The cultural beliefs system of a set of people determine their approach to and responses regarding alcohol and drug abuse (Abbott and Chase, 2008). According to Chia *et al.*, (2015), psychoactive drugs are used for different reasons, including: traditional rites, religious ceremonies, treatment of ailments, pleasurable effects, the urge to find acceptance in a particular group, relaxation or stress relief, to forget ones problems, satisfy curiosity and so on. In Nigeria, different cultural settings have their culturally accepted alcohol drinks and foods as part of the elements of their society. Traditional rituals and other forms of cultural activities from the various ethnic groups in Nigeria have specified accepted alcohol drinks and substances as traditional items or requirements (Peters, 2020). This cultural acceptability has formed culture of alcohol and drug use among ethnic groups in Nigeria. According to Heath (2001), culture is a key factor in creating human's expectations about possible challenges one may encounter in drug abuse. The use of drugs by many social groups may be as a form of providing protection factor, as alcohol use was determined by the ancient Aztecs they come in contact with the Europeans (Abbott and Chase, 2008).

In some parts of Nigeria, the use of these alcohol drinks and drugs have culturally implied importance and the absence of some of these traditional items means inability to conduct or take part in traditional rites and rituals, and it's an inability to convene or satisfy the people which often led to the provocation of the wrath of traditions of the people and

their deities especially among the African traditional religionists. As part of enculturation of these traditions, some parts of Nigeria have selected traditional items for youths. Cultural patterns of use of alcohol and drugs, are passed from one generation to another. Drug abuse in an increasing phenomenon among youths in Nigeria with the increase in knowledge of risk factors and efforts by diverse social, governmental and non-governmental institutions to reduce the pace at which this problem grows within the Nigerian society. The danger of alcohol and drugs abuse by youths in Nigeria has gotten to a frightening level and it is pervading every area of the society (Yusuf *et al.*, 2014).

Youths characterized the largest portion of the Nigerian population both at urban centres and rural areas (NPC, 2006). The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) cited in Peters (2020) stated that the way and the intent to which adolescent use and misuse alcohol and drugs has become a created a high level of concern in Nigeria especially, among students. In every culture, the majority of the traditional and cultural activities are carried out or performed by the youths under the supervision, command and authority of the elders as upholders and overseers of the culture and belief patterns of the people (Peters, 2020). This scenario creates patterns of culture of use of alcohol and drugs, which the majority of the youths have over the years often seized to abuse the use of illicit substances hence, the many cases of drug abuse. Cultural values have a great influence on people's attitudes toward the use of alcohol and drug abuse. Among the Akwa Ibom people, traditional rites and other cultural activities have formed patterns of culture of alcohol and drug use among the people within the society (Peters, 2019). These acculturation patterns have offered the youth opportunities to demand, produce, sell, use and abuse alcohol and drugs. The scenario becomes worse the elders who were once youths, consumers of alcohol and drugs, and abusers of alcohol and drugs are the custodians of the culture of drug use among the people and have over the years defended the portions of the youths and transfer same from one generation to another. This has created high impacts of alcohol and drug

abuse under the disguise of carrying out traditions and cultural activities, as the majority of the youths are dependent on alcohol, drugs and other illicit substances consumption, engaging in deviant behaviours (Peters, 2019), and are having mental health issues which are not just family burdens, but a societal burden. A lot of research has been done on roles of alcohol and drug abuse on youths' health, development, and crime. Chia, *et al.*, (2015) have presented the use of psychoactive drugs for different reasons including traditional rites and observations, religious ceremonies, and treatment of ailments or palliatives, but the impact of the cultural perspective that provides the legitimate right to drink alcohol and take drugs by the youths have been neglected, which is the gap for the study. On this note, this research sought to examine the impacts of the culture of alcohol and drug abuse among youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study sought to examine the impacts of the culture of alcohol and drug abuse among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Examine how the culture of alcohol and drug abuse enhances distorted values among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State
- ii. Investigate how the culture of alcohol and drug abuse influences formation of cycle of drug and substance abuse and addiction among youths and family members in Iman Ibom Clan, Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State
- iii. Investigate people perceptions on the roles of “mkpomkparawa” as pattern of alcohol and drug abuse among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State

- iv. Examine how the culture of alcohol and drug abuse influences criminal behaviours among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions considered to guide the study by the researcher were;

- i. how does the culture of alcohol and drug abuse enhances distorted values among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. how does the culture of alcohol and drug use influences formation of cycle of drug and substance abuse, and addiction among youths and family members in Iman Ibom Clan, Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State?
- iii. how does “mkpomkparawa” (*Traditional Youths Items*) enhances creation of patterns of alcohol and drug abuse among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State?
- iv. how does the culture of alcohol and drug abuse influence criminal behaviours among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The significance of the study is in unravelling the benefits accruing from this work on the roles and importance of human culture. It will present data on the roles of culture in alcohol use and substance abuse by rural youths through cultural or traditional activities, which will create an academic will to undertake a review of alcohol and substance abuse among young people in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study will create the motivation for a review of culture and traditions that enhance alcohol and other psychoactive substance

abuse by youths through existing traditional patterns of cultural activities like traditional marriage ceremonies, burial rites, chieftaincy coronation ceremonies, child dedication ceremonies, and family meetings within the socio-cultural institutions. This implies that it will help the government and custodians of traditions to review the traditional practices that enhance alcohol and substance use and possibly control the quantity of alcohol and drug inclusion in cultural activities and traditions.

The findings of this research therefore will contribute to the wealth of scientific works in alcohol and drug abuse with specific concentration on the roles of culture and traditions and rural youth's involvement. This study will help the formulation of new alcohol and drug policies and illuminate new areas of concern for law enforcement agencies on alcohol and drug abuse. This research also serves as material and literature for others. It is hoped to assist both governmental and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) that work on alcohol and drug addicts' cases, rehabilitation, and drug-induced patient treatments.

1.6 Scope of the Study

This study was undertaken in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It examined roles of cultural practices in enhancing alcohol and drug abuse among Iman Ibom youths in the Iman Ibom Clan within the Etinan Local Government Area. The study concentrated on four variables, namely; distorted values, the formation of a cycle of alcohol and drug abuse, mkpo-mkparawa (youth's items), and criminal and violent behaviours. The main study participants were Iman Ibom people aged 15 years and above from rural Etinan Local Government Area communities. The Social Learning Theory and the Social Bonding Theory were adopted by the researcher to provide theoretical explanations for the study. These theories formed the framework for the fact findings.

Analysis of data was qualitatively done based on key themes derived from each of the objective of the study.

1.7 Clarification of Terms

In the attempt to ascertain a good clarity and proper understanding of the study, the researcher defines some of the terms which serve as variables of the study, as used in the research.

- A. Alcohol:** In this study, alcohol is considered as liquor or any liquid content with capacity to influence and induced behaviour with depressant effect.
- B. Drug Abuse:** This refers to the acts of excessive use of alcohol and other psychoactive substances with depressant effects.
- C. Mkpo-mkparawa (Youths' items):** This refers to the various traditional accepted items for youths which include alcohol like beer, ethanol, palm wine, and hot drinks, and psychoactive substances like raw tobaccos leaves, grinded tobaccos, cigarettes, and other food items.
- D. Distorted values:** These refer to the behaviours exhibited by youths which positioned the youths across the moral codes and boundaries of the society.
- E. Criminal and violent behaviour:** This refers to anti-social acts engage by youths which are considered to be violent in some cases and deviance among the people of the society.
- F. Youths:** This refers to young persons as culturally accepted by the people of Iman Ibom Clan to be between the age of eighteen (18) years and fifty (50) years.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Alcohol, Drug Abuse and Youth's Distorted Values

Since the beginning of the twenty-first century, and even earlier, scientists and other researchers have been studying issues related to alcohol and drug abusers as types of human behaviour especially among the youths (Uoro, *et al.*, 2020). Adolescents and young people are the age range in which people typically pick up more human characteristics and societal acceptable moral codes and norms as they grow from childhood to maturity in order to fit in with their surroundings (Peters, *et al.*, 2023). Youths are more vulnerable to alcohol consumption because of their developing cognitive-control system and increased sensitivity to stimulating effects (Casey, *et al.*, 2011). Those who are used to drinking alcohol may likely not have reserves and may be more willing to entertain the risks, and this is because a lot of them are doing experiment with some of the societal accepted behaviour set for age cohort, especially vulnerable young people (Anonymous, 2024). Youths now choose to use alcohol more than other drugs, and teenagers who drink excessively early in life cause issues for themselves, those around them, and society at large (Myadze and Rwomire, 2014). A verbal confrontation and heavy alcohol consumption typically precede violent acts, which normally lead to either the victim or the perpetrator is likely to be the one who start confrontation. The individual who engaged in the quarrel is mostly going to be a drunk (Murdoch *et al.*, 2000).

Osei-Bonsu *et al.*, (2017) is of the opinion that the consequences that typically accompany alcohol consumption in youth have continued to be a hot topic and a source of concern for parents, educators, governments, and the general public. The frequency of intoxication rather than the frequency of drinking is a stronger indicator of illicit behaviour.

If drinking alcohol is defined by the frequency of intoxication, then a significant portion of young adults who drink and abuse drug substances also engage in disorderly and abnormal behaviour (Richardson and Budd, 2003). Teenagers who consume alcohol and other psychoactive substances are mostly prone to reckless behaviour and most of them do not use contraceptives when getting involve are sexual activities. One in every eight females and one in every ten boys of 15 and 16 years were found to engage in rough and dangerous sexual activities after taking alcohol, which increased their opportunities of being pregnant and infected with sexual transmitted diseases (STDs) (Anonymous, 2024).

According to Richardson and Budd (2003), there exist a statistical link between excessive alcohol intake and unlawful conduct among individuals aged from eighteen to twenty-four years, particularly in males. The findings of an inquiry on the alcohol consumption patterns of 100 English Borstal trainees, which was based on earlier Scottish research, reported that a significant percentage (38%) of the youths who are committed to drinking alcohol in the study admitted to abusing drug also before they execute either current violation or one from the past (Hollin, 2003). In a study conducted by Tiruneh *et al.*, (2015), youths who engage in excessive intake of alcohol drinking and other forms of drugs abuse are likely to exhibit poor behaviour in the society. Young people who indulge in excessive alcohol drink are likely to behave carelessly and have the problems with cognitive ability, and the young people who drink alcohol and involve in abuse of drugs likely to get themselves into crises and conflictual situation (Anonymous, 2024).

According to Usoro *et al.*, (2015), binge consumption of alcohol among the Latino men as understudied by Machismo, brings about antisocial behaviour within their quest to culturally project their masculinity in their society. Alcohol use is rising in sub-Saharan Africa, an area where HIV prevalence is already high and puts young people at risk (Osaki *et al.*, 2018). According to Peters *et al.*, (2022), some youths in Nigeria are consuming new combination substance like hymn N0. 4 (a traditional alcoholic brew with drug substances),

in a traditional manner; they are thinking that consuming combined psychoactive substances will provide them with a high level of emotional satisfaction; and they are pushing the boundaries of morality through traditions to include the acceptance of psychoactive substances like those that are brewed locally. It is especially challenging to evaluate alcohol consumption as a major factor behind antisocial behaviour accurately among adolescents in Africa since the majority of alcohol consumption is attributed to traditional prepared beverages, or homebrew (Seekles *et al.*, 2023).

According to Williams (2001), a market research conducted in Africa for the National Alcohol Campaign by the Commonwealth Department of Health and Aged Care, shown that a considerable percentage of young people have either witnessed or experienced alcohol-related aggressiveness and violence. Negative alcohol-related experiences are also widespread among this youthful age cohort. However, young people hold the view that favourable results are more probable to come about and are most highly valued, despite the significant number of recent encounters with adverse consequences associated with drinking. On the other hand, heavy drinkers perceive negative consequences as more unlikely to happen and weigh those conditions lower than do those who do not drink (Williams, 2011). Alcohol and drug abuse is engaging in consumption of materials whose chemical effects have the potential to alter biological function of the abuser (Peters, 2019).

According to Taylor and Carroll (2001), study shown that young people who engage in excessive alcohol drinking and other substance abuse encountered or engage in some possible problems from binge drinking of alcohol. Fact shown that two out of every three teenagers said they had seen violence caused by a drunk and looked at friend who had taken excessive alcohol was particularly noteworthy. More women than men reported having this experience (73% versus 61%) while 22% of girls said it had taken place frequently (Taylor and Carroll, 2001). Teenage drinking and other substance abuse in

particular has a detrimental effect on an adolescent's academic, emotional, social, and physical development, making it a serious global health concern (Seekles *et al.*, 2023).

According to Seekless *et al.* (2023), increased intake of alcohol use among late adolescence as well as young adulthood is linked to alcohol-related issues, such as dependence which enhance anti-social behaviour. Despite the fact that drug and alcohol misuse alters a young person's brain's ability to perceive challenges and issues of life, there has been a steady rise in the percentage of students abusing or using stimulants (Peters *et al.*, 2023). Teenagers who consume alcohol are more susceptible to its negative effects and are more prone to find themselves in risky or contentious circumstances (Alcohol Concern, 2014).

2.1.2 Culture of Alcohol and Drug Use and Formation of Cycle of Alcohol and Drug Abuse among Youths

Cultural norms and traditional practices are forms of strong predictors of binge alcohol consumption and substance abuse (Usono *et al.*, 2015, 2018; Peters, 2019, 2020^a, 2020^b, 2022, 2023 and Wilson *et al.*, 2020). In many cultures across the world, alcohol is an essential component of social interaction. Colleagues can bond over alcohol, it's an opportunity to appreciate seniors, and it can even kick off business meetings (Gavin, 2023). Researches like Stanley *et al.*, (2009) and Strycker, *et al.*, (2003) examining the causes and conditions surrounding young people's initial alcohol consumption mostly identify peer, parental, and adult influences as key interpersonal factors and. African social situations and special occasions have always included alcohol use and other psychoactive substances as components and symbols of celebration and entertainment, a practice known as traditional rituals (Willis 2011). According to Peters (2019), culture presents youth with opportunities to consume alcohol and psychoactive substances like tobacco, cigarettes, and petrol as are contained in the traditional marriage youths; items of the Ibibio people of

Nigeria. According to study conducted by Osaki *et al.*, (2023), the results unequivocally reveal that interventions aimed at reducing alcohol and psychoactive substance use have to take into consideration of the social environment whereby alcohol is abuse and involve the socially important players within it. Physical and social space makes up the social environment where people interact and share drinks and other consuming substances (Veenstra, 2007). According to Veenstra (2007), people in the society engage in a variety of "social spaces," some of which have a big impact on influencing or limiting the drinking habits of young people.

The most often mentioned factors influencing young people's first-time alcohol usage were parental and peer pressure, with peer influence being more prevalent, especially among young men (Osaki *et al.*, 2018). Youth who often connect with their peers and drink can be readily persuaded to do so, depending on the characteristics of their social environment. Their results suggest that the higher rates were reported of at the beginning and drinking of alcohol among youths relative to young women from the study locations may be partially explained by increased peer pressure among young guys to consume alcohol. According to other research on juvenile alcohol use, peers who drink also drink with their non-drinking peers, while peers who generally disapprove of drinking are associated with lower alcohol usage (Handren *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, a study found that when parents provide alcohol in the home, they frequently fail to take safeguards regarding the amount of alcohol that is deemed dangerous (Gillgan *et al.*, 2013). As a matter of fact, drug abuse behaviour is greatly ascribed to the peer group influence and communication with elders, colleagues, and associates who are already abusers or alcohol and substance induced persons (Usono *et al.*, 2017).

According to Gilbertson *et al.*, (2008), that alcoholism runs in families is commonly known. Moreover, family pedigree, and adoption studies, consistently point to genetic risk rather than familial transmission as the cause of alcohol dependence. Although estimates

vary, it is generally agreed that even if an alcoholic parent is not raised, the likelihood of an offspring developing alcoholism is about four times higher than that of someone without such a history. The majority of early studies focused on male children of male alcoholics (Gilbertson *et al.*, 2008).

According to Massawe *et al.*, (2022), the consumption of alcohol has been part of some people's life in Tanzania since they were three years old. Parents, grandparents gave Alcohol and other substance as a traditional bananas brewed drink, which often assist them to sleep and grow up as strong men. Therefore, being raised by parents meant growing up drinking always, thereby making the act of drinking alcohol a normal life (Massawe *et al.*, 2022). Unaware of the harmful consequences drugs can have on people's health and social interactions, a higher percentage of displaced people take drugs as analgesics, palliatives, or medical treatments (Usono *et a.*, 2017). Understanding the offence cycle requires an awareness of the bidirectional connection of alcohol abuse and the negative impacts as well as the fact that self-control deficiencies could not just characterise alcohol usage and bad effect, but play a role in the offending activity itself (Day *et al.*, 2003).

The generating factors for alcoholism and other psychoactive substances are age, gender, associated mental and drug use disorders, and family history within specific society (Gilbertson *et al.*, 2008). According to Woochang (2008), it was during the Koryo Dynasty (946–943) that Korea developed an interest in producing its own alcohol as a result of contact with foreign cultures and introduction of alcohol, which laid the groundwork and the method of producing a distinctive alcohol. In Korea, drinking alcohol fosters the development of relationships between friends and family. Drinking is a common part of customary family rites including paying respect to ancestors. Apart from the customary drinking during holidays and family get-togethers, alcohol use has evolved and is now a significant part of daily socialisation in Korean culture (Woochang, 2008).

According to Neufeld and Rehm (2013), Russia continues with some the highest rates of consumption of alcohol worldwide. Heavy drinking has detrimental impacts on Russia's social cohesion and has implications for the country's politics, economy, and public health. Because alcohol drinking is a common and culturally accepted social behaviour among the Russians and it is a significant source of revenue for the Russian government for ages, alcoholism has been an issue throughout the nation's history. Germany has a very strong drinking culture, especially when it comes to beer. In 2013, there were 28 litres of beer consumed annually per capita in Germany (Nelson, 2013). Alcoholism is a problem as well; according to a 2022 survey, part of the population is classified as "*dangerous drinkers*" (Garnett *et al.*, 2022). While some cultures stigmatise alcohol use, other culture have high accommodative tolerance on alcohol. Cultural traditions, customs, and manhood expectations influence drinking attitude of people in some culture (Orford, 2005).

According to Neufeld and Rehm (2013), there is differences in drinking patterns across the nations of the world. Wine and beer are an essential part of dining in many European nations, which reflects cultural moderation and drinking with meal. On the other hand, the high rates of consumption of strong alcohol, connect to health and social problems that are seen in nations like Russia. Additionally, alcohol is forbidden by religion in some Islamic nations, which has a significant impact on drinking customs (Neufeld and Rehm, 2013). People's cultural traditions influence not just how they seek health care but also how they live their lives in terms of social interactions, how well society functions (Esen and Peters, 2023), their drinks and foods consumption within the society. Drinking alcohol is thought to improve social relationships within the extended family and with ancestors. They are utilised to commemorate significant social events, life transitions like marriage, death, and widowhood (Bryceson, 2002).

According to Peters *et al*, (2023), it is impossible to fully analyse the roles that culture plays in substance misuse without taking into account the cultural experiences and the influence of traditional rituals on those who abuse these substances. Numerous academic studies have demonstrated the significant influence that cultural practices, such as traditional rites, have on drug acceptability, drug usage, and the extent of misuse of psychoactive substances. Certain cultural contexts provide several cultural grounds for substance and alcohol misuses which present the fact that over the years, alcohol drinking is a significant aspect of a lot of cultural societies (McGovern, 2009). Jiloha (2009) asserts that drug abuse is a multifaceted challenge with range of economic, geographic, cultural, historical, and biological issues. In addition to cultural norms, the collapse of the traditional family system, the lack of parental care and love in modern family structure especially where both parents are working, the deterioration of the moral value system and religious institutions, have contribute to the rise in the number of young drug and alcohol addicts who consider drugs abuse as a coping mechanism to bad economic level of life.

According to Room (2013), at the height of the temperance campaign, American culture underwent a change. Within the framework of that movement, it was contended that alcohol consumption became a focal point for the possible explanation of negative incidents or conduct, as Americans began to perceive alcohol as an extraordinarily potent drug that not only rendered drinkers foolish but also caused them to act in ways they would not want to when sober. In such a setting, drinking alcohol and eventually being addicted became socially acceptable ways to alleviate depression and transition out of sobriety (Room, 2013).

In Africa, everyday life involves alcohol in one way or another, especially in rural areas where distribution and manufacturing are tightly entwined with use (Bryceson, 2002). Its role in African religious belief as a means of communication with the ancestors has always been crucial. Additionally, drinking serves as a hub for socialising and leisure in

both urban and rural settings. Long recognised for its ability to stimulate social interchange, face-to-face social interaction is highly valued in agrarian civilizations across the continent due to oral cultural transmission (Bryceson, 2002).

2.1.3 Mkpomkparawa (Traditional Youths' Items) and Creation of Culture of Alcohol and Drug among Youths

According to Osei-Bonsu *et al.*, (2017), alcohol is among the first substances that youths use before they move to other dangerous substances like cocaine, marijuana, and the rate in which they consume this harmful substance that were previously unavailable to adolescents has unexpectedly increased due to global market modernization and increased advertising. Research indicates that these set of humans start drinking alcohol at adolescence age; yet, more research is required to determine how alcohol use starts in order to create treatments that work for this group of people (Osaki *et al.*, 2018). In United Kingdom, binge and alcohol consumption is part of day-to-day life for young people, yet there are gaps in the resources available to them when it comes to alcohol education and assistance (Alcohol Concern, 2014). Within the pretext level of cultural knowledge, various young people have diverse interpretations of what binge alcoholism and psychoactive drug use and drug abuse mean. While some young individuals use and abuse psychoactive drugs and alcohol with full awareness, others do so out of ignorance and as a laid down way of life (Peter and Bassey, 2022).

Many cultural practices promote cycle of alcohol and substance abuse for young people. According to Garvin (2023), in the UK, 'cheering' in the bar is a very common practice. Furthermore, it's common knowledge that leaving the bar without purchasing a round has some sort of social stigma. For instance, after you've finished drinking, you should cover your empty glass with a coaster in the Czech Republic. If not, they will continue to load you up and assume that you want more. It is culturally maintain that

maintaining eye contact is crucial while clinking glasses with someone in Germany. You will be cursed with seven years of horrible sex if you don't. Certain drinking customs have deeper, more profound origins. Drinking habits can indicate one's level of respect or disrespect in Japan. When you drink while out with co-workers, look away from supervisors and senior employees to avoid offending them (Garvin, 2023). Osei-Bonsu *et al.*, (2017) reports that in Ghana, due to increased marketing, competition, and consumer demand for alcoholic products, many alcoholic drinks are now cheaper than non-alcoholic drinks. Because of these variations, the majority of youth start drinking heavily earlier in life than they used to. According to Usoro *et al.*, (2018), it is culturally acceptable by some cultural groupings to consume alcohol provided that they do not exceed the limit of control.

Globally, there are differences in acceptable drinking times as well which present continual cycle of alcohol drinking and drug abuse. Garvin (2023) further maintain that alcohol consumption is typically limited to the evenings in Britain since they believe it is a little strange to begin drinking before noon. Similar patterns are observed in other nations such as the Czech Republic and Iceland. Drinkers in Iceland typically start their nights out around midnight and stay out late. In other nations, drinking during the day is more acceptable. In Germany, France, Russia, and Spain, having alcohol with lunch is a common practice. In Germany, going out for a drink on Sunday mornings is customary and is referred to as "Frühschoppen." This dates back to the days when Sunday morning church services were followed by family get-togethers at the tavern. It's crucial to keep in mind that, unlike in the UK, where heavy drinking sessions may be more prevalent on weekends, daytime drinking is still restricted in nations where it is prevalent (Garvin, 2023). While other countries in Europe have different reasons for creating culture of alcohol drinking, In Africa,

According to Usoro *et al.*, (2018), factors like arrival of a new born baby, circumcision of the new born babies especially the male child after 8 days of birth and rite

of passage of age grade forms cycle of legitimate alcohol consumption among the Anaang people of Nigeria. When it comes to drinking, nations differ in more ways than merely customs and traditions. Global drinking regulations also differ (Garvin, 2023). Osaki *et al.*, (2018) report that a study was carried out in Tanzania's Mwanza and Kilimanjaro areas, which were specifically chosen due to their disparate drinking cultures. Kilimanjaro has more liberal attitudes around young people alcohol consumption and higher alcohol consumption than Mwanza. Due to the abundance of businesses, educational facilities, and plantations, these regions were good for attracting young people and students to the formal sector and the liberal norms toward youth alcohol consumption, a lot of young take to binge alcoholism and drug abuse.

Local cultural norms are important variables that can impact alcohol consumption (Nwagu, *et al.*, 2017). Ekeke and John (2023) report that Nigeria's traditional religion and society make alcoholic drinking very rampant among the youths. Particularly prevalent times for this abuse are the New Yam festivities, as well as the Ekpe, Ekpo, and Nmanwu masquerade festivals, funeral rites, and naming ceremonies. Some argue that this is motivated by some African cultural practices and beliefs, such as libations, hospitality, entertaining strangers and guests, and the quest to uphold the culture of the people (Ekeke and John, 2023). Peters (2019) reports that cultural practices like burial rites, traditional marriage ceremony, child dedication ceremony, and cultural display are traditional factors enhancing alcohol and drugs abuse among youths in southern part of Nigeria. In Nigeria, the traditional marriage list of the people in the southern region of the nation especially among the Ibibio includes alcohol and psychoactive substances like tobacco, cigarettes, and penetrol (Peters, 2019).

According to Osei-Bonsu *et al.*, (2013), another concerning issue in youth alcohol drinking is the early contact with alcohol. A poll conducted in the United States of America, young individuals often start drinking alcohol at the age of fifteen. According to another

Thai-language survey, the majority of Thai who drink alcohol (74.7%) are within the age of 15, and the youths start consuming this alcohol between the ages of 15 and 24. This implies that the average age of attempt to use substance was found to be between 14 and 19 years old, while the largest age range for substance use was found to be between 16 and 23 years old from a study on substance abuse among the second cycle and the out-of-school adolescents in Ghana. Furthermore, drugs that are mainly taken by Ghanaian youth, and the most commonly used drugs by Ghanaian adolescents include heroin, alcohol, cigarettes, and cannabis (Osei-Bonsu *et al.*, 2013).

2.1.4 Culture of Alcohol and Drug Use and Criminal Behaviour among Youths

According to Udoh *et al.*, (2016), those classified as binge drinkers; those who, on one occasion, can drink up to five or more standard alcohol drinks (such as a 12-ounce beer for males and four or more for women) perpetrated sexual violence crime at a higher rate than those who did not engage in excessive alcohol drinking. Hagler (2024) posits that numerous violent crimes, including suicide, murder, assault, and domestic abuse, are brought on by alcohol. According to Richardson and Budd (2003), alcohol-related criminal activities are widely spread acknowledged phenomenon among towns and cities within many leisure areas. Excessive alcohol or binge consumption has been specially linked with alcohol-related criminal disorders. According to research, youths are the demographic cohort that is mostly prone to involving in criminal activities, be unstable, and binge drink (Richardson and Budd, 2003).

According to Hagler (2024), alcohol and drug abuse have significant effect on violent crimes such as assault, rape, murder, and abuse of children and spouses. Among crimes involving alcohol, drunk driving typically receives the greatest attention and is protected by numerous laws; however, research on alcohol and violent crimes is equally necessary to assist keep these crimes from occurring as frequently in the future. Day *et al.*,

(2003) posits that it is widely recognised that alcohol consumption is closely linked to criminal activity for a large number of offenders. In rehabilitation centres, rehabilitation programmes are employed to prevent relapse, alcohol consumption is included as a "criminogenic need" due to the widespread professional assumption that the two occurrences are related, most likely in a causative way (Day *et al.*, 2003). The likelihood of engaging in fighting or violent crime was more than five times higher for those who consumed alcohol on a weekly basis. Those who consumed alcohol at least once a week, was considered to be seven-times capable of being part of or initiating breaking or damaging of something, and a five-time increase among those who are likely to get into a fight for quarrel or deviant behaviour that occurred while or after involving in drinking (Richardson and Budd, 2003).

According to Manso *et al.*, (2010), binge alcohol practice and substance abuse among the young people have become an indirect influencer for teenage delinquency. The late adolescent delinquent involvement was linked to dangerous sex, excessive alcohol consumption problem, and youths' criminal behaviours. This also exerts a lasting impact on deviants and criminal activities. The link between dangerous sexual behaviour and criminal tendencies was also recognized through their misbehaviour due to binge alcohol abuse. Excessive drinking and increase in drinking during adolescence were predicted by early alcohol use, and this in turn revealed young adult alcohol drinking problems and hazardous sex (Manson *et al.*, 2010). There is ample evidence connecting excessive alcohol and other psychoactive substance intake to youth-related violence (Alcohol Concern, 2014).

Alcohol use rises gradually during adolescence and delinquency is more likely to be prediction of alcohol consumption than the other way around (Muthén and Muthén, 2000). Risky sex, alcohol use disorders, and early adult criminality are all known to be affected negatively by adolescent misbehaviour. According to this research, the

associations between youths from low-income were more pronounced compare to the youths from the middle-class (Mason *et al.*, 2010). Mason *et al.*, (2010) also maintain that five self-report questionnaires measuring the frequency of violent and vandal behaviours in relation to binge alcohol and substance abuse among teenagers were used to gauge delinquency at the ages of 14, 15, 16, and 18. It was found that excessive alcohol and substance abuse are responsible for delinquent among young people of 14, 15, 16, and 18 years of age in Europe.

According to nidirect.com (2024), the likelihood of an adolescent to commit a crime is less expected of the adolescents who take alcohol at least once in a month. Young people who consume alcohol every week are more predictable to be involve in violent criminal activities like robbery or assault. Indirect.com further reports that among the school-age children in secondary school, four out of ten had experienced violence related to binge alcohol. This could indicate that they have assaulted someone personally or that they have been robbed or beaten up after drinking. According to Hagler (2024), violence and alcohol have long been serious subjects in society since they can both be abnormal in certain situations. These two problems (alcohol and violence) have contributed significantly to crime, deaths, and social damage. However, the combination of alcohol and violence makes them considerably more deadly (Hagler, 2024).

According to Roman and Reid (2012), drinking alcohol is positively correlated with domestic violence, particularly on the weekends. Alcoholism is a major contributing factor in many acts of self-harm and delinquency, as well as acts of domestic violence where victims attack their spouse or significant other. Few researches particularly address the link between abuse of alcohol and domestic violence, despite the fact that many broad studies on the subject have been conducted. Given that domestic violence is still aggressive behaviour, it stands to reason that persons who drink alcohol will still behave violently and

antagonistically with their own spouse. This is specifically true provided they have prior knowledge that have made them more violent towards other people (Hagler, 2024).

According to Sung (2016), alcohol misuse is usually co-occurring with domestic violence. Of victims of domestic abuse, two thirds have reported drinking alcohol. Intimate violence is more common among moderate drinkers than among light and abstainers; yet, heavy and/or binge drinkers are typically the ones that engage in the most persistent and severe types of aggression. Alcohol usage is positively connected with the likelihood, frequency, and intensity of physical attacks. Following behavioural treatment for marital drinking tend to bring about aggression declines. Additionally, research indicates that alcohol misuse and child maltreatment may be related (Sung, 2016). Driving a motor car being inebriated with alcohol and drugs is known as driving under the influence (DUI) or driving while intoxicated (DWI) (Nelson, 2017). Blood alcohol content, or BAC, is a common way to evaluate how drunk a motorist is after consuming alcohol. However, BAC can also be stated as a breath test result, which is commonly referred to as a BAC. Without requiring proof of impairment, a BAC measurement above a given threshold level, such 0.08%, designates a criminal offence. There is an aggravated category for the offence in some countries, with BAC levels as high as 0.12%, 0.15%, or 0.25%. Police officers can put a suspects through field-tests in several jurisdictions to check for indicators of substance intoxication (Nelson, 2017).

Abuse of alcohol and other drugs raises a person's chance of encountering or committing sexual violence (Chersich and Rees, 2010). Drug-Facilitated Sexual Assault (DFSA) refers to sexual assaults which take place after the victim has used drugs or alcohol to the point of incapacitating themselves. Due to its accessibility and legality, alcohol is still the most often utilised predator drug and it is believed to be used in the majority of sexual assaults. Because their victims frequently consume alcohol voluntarily and may be encouraged to consume enough to lose consciousness or inhibitions, many attackers

employ alcohol. In most, if not all jurisdictions, having sexual intercourse with an unconscious victim is straight away considered as rape. Some attackers have even committed "rapes of convenience," in which the victim is attacked after they've fallen asleep from drinking as well (Chersich and Rees, 2010). Sung (2016) maintained that alcohol usage is positively correlated with robbery and other offences, these crimes are mostly linked to alcohol use. In a study, consumption of alcohol was responsible for 15% of armed robberies cases, 63% of cases were intimate partner violence crimes, sexual assaults were 37%, physical assaults cases were 45–46%, and the killings in US were 40–45% (McMurrin, 2012). According to a 1983 research conducted in the US, 54% of violent crime suspects who were apprehended there had previously used alcohol. 39% of violent criminals in the United Kingdom in 2015–2016 were abusers of alcohol. Comparable research from other countries suggests that alcohol use contributes to roughly 63% of violent crimes committed globally (McMurrin, 2012).

According to William (2001), it seems that alcohol drinking exposes teens and youths to a range of bad experiences in life with alcohol, with violence and aggression playing a prominent role in these events. Teenagers who were not involved in alcohol abuse nevertheless witnessed or experienced violence and hostility related to the abuse of alcohol, even though it is highly correlated with alcohol consumption. Young adults are considered to be more likely to have issues related to alcohol influenced violence than underage drinkers. Over 1.53 million people were incarcerated in US jails for drug-related offences (Freeman *et al.* 2017), and a large proportion of these inmates were men, and roughly half of them had received sentences for drug-related offences (Enamhe and Maxwell-Borjor, 2021). Many young people explicitly linked their drug and alcohol usage to their criminal behaviour (Prichard and Payne, 2005). According to Alcohol Concern (2014), in London, alcohol and cannabis are the two substances that young offenders most frequently use as problem drugs.

2.2 Summary of Literature Review

Review of literature on youths distorted behaviour on alcohol and drug abuse has been revealed by Usoro *et al.*, (2020) that since the beginning of the twenty-first century, and even earlier, scientists and other researchers have been studying issues related to alcohol and drug abusers as types of human behaviour especially among the youths due to the associated consequences. It is revealed by literature that youths now choose to use alcohol more than other drugs, and teenagers who drink excessively early in life cause issues for themselves, those around them, and society at large (Myadze and Rwomire, 2014). Distorted behaviour like verbal confrontation according to Murdoch *et al.*, (2000) is heavily linked to alcohol consumption and typically precedes violent acts, and the victim and the culprit are likely equally likely to start the conflict. It was reported that meanwhile, the individual who began the quarrel is mostly an abuser of alcohol (Murdoch *et al.*, 2000). Anonymous (2024) reported that teenagers who consume alcohol or abuse drugs are more prone to act recklessly and not utilise birth control provisions when they are sexually active or engage in sex. It is reported that as part of distorted behaviour under the influence of alcohol, one in every eight females, and one in every ten males ages 15 and 16 engaged in dangerous behaviour after consuming alcohol which increases their chance of unintended pregnancy and sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) infections (Anonymous, 2024). Richardson and Budd (2003) report that there exists a statistical correlation between excessive usage of alcohol and unlawful conduct among young individuals aged from eighteen to twenty-four years, particularly in males

Reviewed literature on culture as a cycle of alcohol, drugs and other psychoactive substance abuse revealed that due to the continuous concern on the roles of alcohol and drug abuse in societal problems, a lot of research has been done on the roles and impact of culture of alcohol and drug abuse. Literature like Usoro *et al.*, (2015); (2018), Peters (2019); (2020)^a; (2020)^b; (2022); (2023) and Wilson *et al.*, (2020) opined that cultural

norms and traditional practices are forms of strong predictors influence excessive alcohol consumption and substance abuse. Gavin (2023) is of the opinion that in many cultures across the world, alcohol is an essential component of social interaction, with colleagues activating bonding over alcohol, alcohol drink becomes an opportunity to appreciate seniors, and it can even kick off business meetings across cultures. Alcohol intake has been revealed by literature to be given legitimacy at the family levels across many nations of the world. According to Gilbertson *et al.*, (2008), it is well known that there is an established fact that alcoholism runs in families. Family pedigree, and adoption studies, consistently point to genetic risk rather than familial transmission as the cause of alcohol dependence. The most often mentioned factors influencing young people's first-time alcohol usage were members of the family like parents (Osaki *et al.*, 2018).

Reviewed literature on the youth items (mkpo-mkparawa) as cultural legitimacy for alcohol and drug abuse, Usoro *et al.*, (2018) revealed that factors like the arrival of a newborn baby, circumcision of the newborn babies especially the male child after 8 days of birth and rite of passage of age grade forms cycle of legitimate alcohol consumption which young people found as social and cultural provision among the Anaang people of Nigeria. Peters (2019) reports that cultural practices like burial rites, traditional marriage ceremonies, child dedication ceremonies, and cultural displays are traditional factors enhancing alcohol and drug abuse among youths in the southern part of Nigeria. Literature on the issue from researchers shows that in Germany, going out for a drink on Sunday mornings is customary and is referred to as "Frühschoppen." This dates back to the days when Sunday morning church services were followed by family get-togethers at the tavern. It's crucial to keep in mind that, unlike in the UK, where heavy drinking sessions may be more prevalent on weekends, daytime drinking is still restricted in nations where it is prevalent (Garvin, 2023).

According to Garvin (2023), in the UK, 'cheering' in the bar is a very common cultural practice which enhance young adult intake and drinking of alcohol. Furthermore, it's common knowledge that leaving the bar without purchasing a round has some sort of social stigma among the English people. In Czech Republic, Garvin (2023) reports that culturally, after you've finished drinking, you should cover your empty glass with a coaster. If not, they will continue to load you up and assume that you want more. It is culturally maintained that maintaining eye contact is crucial while clinking glasses with someone in Germany. Otherwise, you will be cursed with seven years of horrible sex if you don't. Certain drinking customs have deeper, more profound origins. Drinking habits can indicate one's level of respect or disrespect in Japan. When you drink while out with co-workers, look away from supervisors and senior employees to avoid offending them (Garvin, 2023). Osei-Bonsu *et al.*, (2017) report that in Ghana, due to increased marketing, competition, and consumer demand for alcoholic products, a lot of alcoholic drinks are now not as costly as compare to non-alcoholic drinks. Because of these variations, the majority of youth start drinking heavily earlier in life than they used to. According to Usoro *et al.*, (2018), it is culturally acceptable by some cultural groupings to consume alcohol.

Reviewed of the literature on the influence of alcohol and drug abuse on crime revealed that according to Hagler (2024), alcohol and drug abuse have a significant effect on violent crimes such as assault, rape, murder, and abuse of children and spouses. Among crimes involving alcohol, drunk driving typically receives the greatest attention and is protected by numerous laws; however, research on alcohol and violent crimes is equally necessary to assist in keeping these crimes from occurring as frequently in the future. Day *et al.*, (2003) posit that it is widely recognised that alcohol consumption is closely linked to criminal activity for a large number of offenders. Hagler (2024) posits that numerous violent crimes, including suicide, murder, assault, and domestic abuse, are brought on by alcohol. According to Richardson and Budd (2003), the issue of crimes caused by abusers

of alcohol and drugs is becoming more visible and known in towns and cities. Excessive alcohol intake has been specifically linked to crimes and disorder. According to research, youths are the demographic cohort that engages in criminal activity, are unstable, and are drunks (Richardson and Budd, 2003). Abuse of alcohol and other drugs raises a person's chance of encountering or committing sexual violence (Chersich and Rees, 2010). Alcohol usage is positively connected with the likelihood, frequency, and intensity of physical attacks. According to nidirect.com (2024), the likelihood of an adolescent to commit a crime is very high as compare to those who don't drink alcohol as much in a month. Teenagers who consume alcohol at least once a week are more likely than not to have engaged in violent crimes like assault or robbery.

It can be concluded from reviewed literature that abuse of alcohol and abuse of drug are rooted in the culture of the nations of the world (Osei-Bonsu *et al.*, 2017; Usoro *et al.*, 2018; Osaki *et al.*, 2018; Peters 2019; 2020; Wilson *et al.*, 2020 and Garvin, 2023). Literatures have shown that alcohol and drug abuse are responsible for the majority violence and crimes around the world today. Young people by reviewed literature engage more in alcohol abuse than other drugs at their early age in life. Youths now choose to use alcohol more than other drugs, and teenagers who drink excessively early in life cause issues for themselves, those around them, and society at large (Myadze and Rwomire, 2014). According to Chersich and Rees (2010), abuse of alcohol and other drugs raises a person's chance of encountering or committing sexual violence.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

The researcher adopted two (2) theories for a theoretical explanation of the theory. These theories are; social learning theory and social bong.

2.3.1. Social Learning Theory

According to Miller (2011), social learning theory is Bandura's theory which explains social behaviour and the learning process; that people are bound to develop new behaviours by observing and imitating others. According to Bandura (2004), learning has to be a cognitive process which takes place within a social setting and can take place even in the absence of motor reproduction or direct reinforcement. Also, it can happen through mere observation or direct teaching. Vicarious reinforcement according to the proponent is the method through which learning takes place when rewards and penalties are considered in addition to conduct. Constant rewards for certain behaviour will increase the tendency that such behaviour will continue; on the other hand, frequent punishments for certain behaviour may increase the tendency that it will stop (Bandura, 1971). The theory goes beyond predictable behavioural theories that explain how to control behaviour. By highlighting the significant roles played by various inner processes in the learning individual, the theory is set on conventional behavioural theories, which hold that behaviour is only measured by supports (Bandura, 1963).

In this theoretical framework, the operant conditioning theories and the pre-existing social learning models were unable to provide a sufficient explanation for the learning processes that Albert Bandura investigated in interpersonal contexts (Bandura, 1971). In particular, Bandura claimed that the dimness of learning methods that mark down the impact of social variables is more exposed than in their conduct of the gaining of original responses (Bandura, 1963). Skinner's theory of how novel answers are learned was based on the successive approximation process, which calls for several tries, reinforcement of certain behavioural components, and incremental modification (Chomsky, 1995). According to Rotter's theory, subjective expectancy and reinforcement value determine how likely conduct is to occur (Chomsky, 1995). Bandura (2004) claimed that because this

model presumed a hierarchy of preexisting answers, it was unable to account for a reaction that had not yet been learnt.

Bandura started researching how quickly people pick up new behaviours through social observation; his most well-known tests used Bobo dolls. To provide a complete model that accounts for the diversity of learning experiences that occur in the real world, the social learning theory fuses the behavioural and the cognitive theories of learning. The key concepts of Social Learning Theory, presented by Bandura and Walters in 1963 and then expanded upon in 1977 (Grusec, 1992), are as follows:

- i. Learning is a process of cognitive abilities that occurs in a social setting rather than being solely behavioural.
- ii. Vicarious reinforcement is a learning process that can take place through watching a behaviour and its results.
- iii. ii. Learning is the process of making decisions about how to conduct a behaviour based on observations, and knowledge garnered from those processes of observations,(also known as modelling or observational learning). So, learning can happen even when there isn't a noticeable behavioural shift.
- iv. iii. Although reinforcement contributes to learning, it is not solely to blame.
- v. iv. The student is not a passive information-gatherer. The interdependence of cognition, environment, and behaviour is known as reciprocal determinism.

Elements of Social Learning Theory

a) Observation and direct experience: Conventional theories of stimulus-response rest solely on the firsthand experience (with the stimulus) which is to be guided behaviour. Presenting observation to be a possibility, Bandura broadens the scope of learning mechanisms (Bandura, 1971). He incorporates modelling, in which is another way that people "represent actual outcomes symbolically" (Bandura, 1963). As conflicting with the real penalties that should be allowed in a typical S-R theory, these cognitively mediated

models permit the future consequences to have an equal impact. The idea of reciprocal determinism is central to the Social Learning Theory. According to this theory, an individual's behaviour affects their environment, just as environment affects the individual's behaviour (Hull, 1990). Put differently, an individual's behaviour, environment and intrinsic characteristics all have a mutual impact on one another. According to Peters (2019), a youngster who engages in violent video games is likely to urge their classmates to play similarly, which in turn motivates other children to play frequently.

b) Modelling and underlying cognitive processes: The Social Learning Theory makes extensive use of the previously discussed modelling approach. Bandura classified modelling stimuli into three categories:

- i. Live models, which feature an individual exhibiting the intended behaviour
- ii. Verbal instruction, in which a person gives a participant step-by-step instructions on how to carry out the desired behaviour.
- iii. Symbolic: This type of modelling uses media, such as radio, television, movies, the Internet, and literature. Characters, whether actual or imaginary, can serve as stimuli.

Several cognitive and behavioural processes, including the type of model, affect exactly what information is extracted from observation (Miller, 2011).

c) Attention: Observers need to pay attention to the modelled behaviour to learn. According to experimental research, understanding the mechanisms of reinforcement and the material being learnt significantly improves learning results (Anderson and Bushman, 2001). Features of the behaviour or action (e.g., novelty, relevance, functional value and affective valence), as well as features of the observer (e.g., perceptual abilities, cognitive capacities, awakening, past performance), influence attention. Social factors can influence attention as: the status of various models influences the usefulness and significance of observations, which in turn modifies attention.

d) Retention: Observers need to be able to recall specific details of the behaviour in order to replicate it. Once more, the event's intricacy and the observer's cognitive capacities and cognitive rehearsal have an impact on this process. According to Bandura, two types of cognitive processes underpin retention: verbal and visual. In more complicated situations, verbal descriptions of models are employed.

e) Reproduction: By "reproduction," Bandura means "application" rather than "propagation" of the model. This calls for some level of cognitive ability as well as, occasionally, sensorimotor skills. Reproduction can be challenging since it can be challenging to watch behaviour correctly when it comes to behaviours that are armoured by self-observation. Others' opinions may be needed to provide self-correcting feedback on this. This theory is supported by more recent research on feedback (Burgess and Akers, 2011), which indicates that participants perform better on tasks when they get effective feedback that aids in observation and correction.

f) Motivation: The observer's expectations and motivations, such as expected outcomes and internal norms, influence the decision to replicate (or not replicate) a witnessed behaviour. Since the useful value of various behaviours in a particular surrounding drives motivational elements, Bandura's account on motivation is thus essentially dependent on the surroundings and consequent social features.

g) Evolution and cultural intelligence: this implies that in recent periods, the theory of cultural intelligence is supported by and used alongside social learning theory (Peters, 2019). Cultural intelligence hypothesis presents people to have certain set of behaviours and abilities which allow them to communicate across the cultural borders (Fuhrmann *et al.*, 2014). This rest on on a theory of human learning which stresses the significance of social learning and clenches the characteristics that increase social learning chances that have been selected for by individuals. This implies that social learning skills, comparable to Bandura's cognitive processes are necessary for modelling, and correlate

with other intelligence and learning, the theory expands on existing social theory (Rear, 2014). Compared to chimpanzees, experimental data demonstrates that humans over-imitate behaviour, supporting the theory that humans have chosen for social learning (Uddin *et al.*, 2007).

Mirror neurons have been linked to the neurophysiology of motor cognition, social cognition, social learning, and observational learning in recent neuroscience studies (Schalk and Burkart, 2011). Human social learning has been strongly associated with mirror neurons. The first known instances of mirror neurons in primates were found during the training of motor activity tasks in monkeys. One such study utilised a hammer to teach primates how to crack nuts. The primate's mirror neuron systems were triggered when it saw someone else using a hammer to crack nuts, and as a result, it learnt how to do the same. On the other hand, learning did not take place and the mirror neuron networks did not activate when the primate was not given a chance to learn socially (Uddin *et al.*, 2007). Analogous research conducted on humans also reveals evidence that the human's mirror neuron structure fires anytime one observes an individual engaging in physical activity. It is believed that goal-directed behaviours and their intention are understood only when the mirror neuron system is activated. This offers a clear neurological connection to comprehending social cognition, even though it is still debatable (Whiten *et al.*, 2009).

2.3.2 Social Bond Theory

According to Wickert (2022), Hirschi in his Social Bond Theory of 1969 assumes that people are inherently inclined to crime. He finds it intriguing to wonder what keeps people from going against the norm. According to Hirschi, social control is what creates conformity. Hirschi separates the four types of social bonds as; attachment, engagement, belief and commitment, and examines how each affects social control. The fundamental premise of Hirschi's social bond theory explains that people have a predisposition towards

delinquency. He observed that it is fascinating to wonder what keeps people from deviating from the communal standard. Hirschi assumes that individuals are likely to behave in line with cultural and traditional norms, the larger the degree of social, cultural and traditional control and the deeper the network of social relationships.

Wickert (2022) posits that Hirschi contests the concept that delinquent teenagers have any noteworthy effect on their peers of the same age cohort by relating his thesis to teenage offenders. Hirschi therefore defines "social bonds" as mechanisms of social cohesiveness which include a robust relationship and bond with one's family, adherence to set up institutions and created acceptable social standards, participation in social and cultural activities, and the belief that all these things are importantly significant.

Robert (2018) posits that according to social bond theory, deviant behaviour is not just managed or caused. To Robert, social bond theories just like other control theories, make the assumption that criminal tendency is innate and natural. Travis Hirschi's (1969) observation and control theories attempt to make an explanation of why people are committing to deviant activities rather than viewing deviance as problem (Robert, 2018).

Elements of Social Bonding Theory

- a) Attachment: The amount of an individual's contacts and interactions with their social environments is characterised by their attachment to the environment. Though the bond with parents is very significant, other social institutions and individuals like friends or school, create an impact. It is explained that deviance can be avoided through social bonding with one's circle of friends, only if this social group does not promote abnormal behaviour (Wickert, 2022). According to Robert (2018) attachment as the first component of the social bond theory by Hirschi, reveals how closely an individual is related to the traditional norm. When Hirschi initially investigated this factor, it exposed an opposite relationship between parents and their peers. This has been a major feature in early control theories. An individual who is extremely perceptive of people's thoughts is likely to show

attachment. Having an emotional attachment to teachers, friends, classmates and parents remains examples of how relationships can stop individuals from getting involve in deviant events due to the fear of losing their emotional bonding with people who have respect for them. Hirschi focused on three distinct relationships when he was discussing attachment as it relates to peers, school, and parents (Robert, 2018).

b) Commitment: The level of commitment devoted to traditional ideals and the aims are refer to as the commitment. Therefore, Hirschi makes the assumption that an individual who might have committed money, time, and other efforts to reach conforming goals may lose more from criminal behaviour than an individual who hasn't considered seeking socially approved aims. For instance, any student stands not to suffer expulsion from school than those who don't care about their grades (Wickert, 2022).

Robert (2018) posits that the second component of the social bond theory by Hirschi is commitment. This becomes the most workable element of acquiescence. It describes the level of effort an individual gives to traditional aims, relationships, or quests. People who have aspirations for their future careers or studies will be discouraged from taking part in deviant behaviour by the prospect of incapability to fulfil ambitious ambitions. Illegal events can create a problem capable of keeping individuals from reaching their aims of creating workable relationships and being part of legal events. Incarceration, for example, stops an individual from finishing their school programmes or attaining the height of their professional prospects. These deviants assess the problems arising from not abiding with the law; if there is much to lose, they tend to consider the challenge as worthless (Robert, 2018).

c) Belief: Hirschi posited that believing is the fourth and next component of social bonding (Wickert, 2022). It has to with the acceptability of the standards and core traditional values of the main culture. (Wickert, 2022). According to Robert (2018), belief stands at the third component in social bonding and relationship. According to Robert,

social consensus on a norm or set of values becomes key to the validation of belief. The internalisation of a moral code and the ability to reject the wrong by accepting the good are key elements of belief. The more an individual believes a set of prescribed rules is morally valid, the less he or she will likely stray away from it. Anybody who does not feel indebted to observing the norms is likely to deviate from the norms because the feeling of bonding to the norms is not there (Robert, 2018).

d) Involvement: To Hirschi, "involvement" is a term that describes the process of individuals' participation in traditional activities which makes these individuals not have the time to engage in deviant activities. This process of conformity is necessary to overcome the pressure of deviant behaviour which is strengthened by socially structured and socially prescribed roles like going to work, going to school and taking care of the children (Wickert, 2022). Robert (2018) posits that involvement is the last component of the social relationship. This component revolves around the idea that the longer one gives to doing traditional duties, the shorter the time it takes to start engaging in deviant behaviour. This factor mostly depends on an individual's availability; that is getting occupied with various traditional roles which reduces an individual's chances to take part in criminal activity. This implies that there is less opportunity for deviant activities as an individual gets deeply involved in either academics, sports or employment.

Robert (2018) maintains that it is important to recognise the relationship between these elements of social bonding. The major idea in this theory is that there is the possibility for deviant behaviour to increase if any of the components of the theory is weakened or becomes much more severe, and this has been validated empirically.

2.3.3 Synthesis of the Theories (Social Learning Theory and Social Bonding Theory)

The following points generalize the synthesis of Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Hirschi's Social Bonding Theory for applicability in line with the objectives of the study:

1. The process of learning and social conduct that results in the acquisition of new behaviours through watching and copying others as a result of attachment. This explains that the culture of alcohol and drug use present the youths with the learning environment to drink alcohol and consume drugs as forms of attachment to members of their families and communities. Also, an attachment in the process with criminal minds will influenced others especially under intoxication.
2. Developed behaviours are accessed differently by individuals based on their cultural continuous interactions with other individuals within the family and community as a form of commitment to traditions. This explains the continuation which leads to the development of abusive behaviour in order to maintain traditions, as well as the drug and alcohol use cycles by young people as expected cultural commitment.
3. Young people form and develop their behaviours through their involvement in imitating actions of other individuals' actions. This explains that through involvement in the traditional practices which present the culture of alcohol and drug use, the possibilities of abusive are present and consequently, influenced deviant behaviour expected.
4. Young people learn cultural elements as a result of the adopted belief system of the community or society. This explains that youths learn to accept and consume alcohol and drugs as part of youths items (Mkpomkparawa) as part of the belief system of their people and their culture.

2.4 Summary

A lot of research has been carried out and findings reported on alcohol and drugs abuse and their related impacts and consequences across the various nations of the world (Abbott and Chase, 2008; Chersich and Rees, 2010; Ekpenyong, 2012; Osei-Bonsu *et al.*, 2017; Osaki *et al.*, 2018; Peters 2019; Usoro *et al.*, 2019; Peters *et al.*, 2020; Garvin, 2023). The reviewed literature shows that alcohol consumption is cultured among the people of the world. The regulation of alcohol consumption varies from one nation to another depending on the cultural practices and cultural position on alcohol. Drug abuse has remained a serious problem among the nations of the world and the most concerned issue is the wide spread of drug abuse among the younger population.

Studies have provided literature on the influence of alcohol and drug abuse on crime among youths (Muthén and Muthén, 2000; Day *et al.*, 2003; Richardson and Budd, 2003; Mason *et al.*, 2010; Roman and Reid 2012; Alcohol Concern, 2014; Richardson and Budd, 2003; nidirect.com 2024; Hagler 2024; Udoh *et al.*, 2016; Sung, 2016 and Nelson, 2017) which indicate that alcohol and drug abuse have great roles in criminal behaviour among young people across the world.

Theoretically, reviewed on Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Hirschi's Social Bonding Theory show the process of learning and social conduct that results in the acquisition of new behaviours through watching and copying others as a result of attachment. Accordingly, this explains that the culture of alcohol and drug use presents the youths with the learning environment and cycle of consumption to drink alcohol and consume drugs as forms of attachment to members of their families and communities. Continuous involvement in alcohol and drug consumption leads to abuse which influences violent and criminal behaviours among young people.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

According to Fetterman (2010), research design is assembling the necessary components of an investigation into a coherent sequence for solving problems. To observe and collect data on the impacts of the culture of alcohol and drug use among the Iman Ibom youths in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, this study used an exploratory research design. This research design has qualitative, descriptive, investigative, and explanatory potentials to generate evidence-based data that was used in examining and explaining substantial issues raised in this study. These potentials are helpful for future research on the various variables that the researcher in this study has identified.

Numerous methods for gathering and analysing qualitative data were possible with this kind of research design. The interview schedule was very useful as a major instrument deployed in gathering primary data for the study. This instrument was couched with questions that addressed the impact of the culture of alcohol and drug abuse among the Iman Ibom youths. An in-depth examination of the impact of cultural influences on alcohol abuse and an assessment of topical issues bothering drug abuse among the youths in the study area was carried out. The interview schedule was designed to ensure that the information collected aligned with the study's specific objectives. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data in line with field information that was gathered.

3.2 The Study Area

The study was conducted in Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Geographically, the local government area is situated between latitude 05° and longitude 07° east. The capital of Akwa Ibom State, Uyo, is 26 kilometres (km)

south of it. Its borders are shared by five (5) more local government areas; Nsit Ibom, Nsit Ubium, Abak, Onna, and Mkpato Enine. Etinan Town, the headquarters, sits halfway between Uyo and Eket on the road network. There are currently sixty-four (64) communities that make up the Etinan Local Government Area. There are eleven (11) political wards made up of these villages. The local government area had 169,284 people living there, out of this, 89,907 were men and 79,377 were women (National Population Commission, 2006).

According to Peters (2020), the Iman Ibom people, who are characterised as lively, inventive, hardworking, and bright, make up the majority of the population in the area. There are Ekpo, Ekong, Ebre, and Idiong societies, among others as their cultural display. Although some African traditional religions are practised by a small minority of people, Christians make up the majority of the population. Through dances, artwork, and crafts, their culture is reflected and promoted. The Iman Ibom people speak the Ibibio language. Pounded cocoyam, pounded yam, Mbud ukom, Etuho Mboro, Asa akpakpa, Asa iwa, Ekpong Nkukwo, foofoo, bitter leaf soup, Ufofop ukpom, sweet yam, and other traditional foods are some of the major daily delicacies.

The rainforest of West Africa contains a sizable amount of fertile land in the Etinan Local Government Area (Peters, 2020). Together with other regions of the state, the land enhances good food production in the local government area. One of the main economic activities that employ the largest percentage of people is agriculture of the Iman Ibom people. Food production sustains a sizable number of households in the local government region. The local government region contains a good amount of agricultural products, including palm oil, cassava, yam, cocoyam, plantains, maize, rice, rubber, and cocoyam.

The main source of income for the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area is small-scale petty trading. Along with several minor but important markets dispersed throughout a few of the local government area's villages, one of the most well-

known markets is the "Udwa Etinan," which is located in the capital. The people's primary means of subsistence are farming and small-scale trading. Many of the individuals also do baking, sculpting, woodcarving, wine tapping, and crafts.

Since the time of the colonial masters, healthcare services have been a part of Etinan Local Government Area's history. The British of the Qua Iboe Mission in Etinan constructed, oversaw, and trained staff in health care services, giving rise to Qua Iboe Hospital, currently known as General Hospital. The local government region is fortunate to have two large general hospitals, the Leprosy Hospital in Ekpene Obom, and other health centres in Etinan and Mbioto Ekpene Ituen. Etinan Local Government Area features a sizable population of civil servants who work both inside and beyond the local government area, despite the fact that the majority of Iman Ibom people are farmers and small-time traders.

The area has 41 public primary schools located in the three main geopolitical zones of Northern Iman, Iman Central, and Southern Iman that make up the Etinan Local Government Area. In addition, there are a lot of private elementary, high, and nursery schools in the local government region. The number of secondary schools in the local government area has increased with the addition of Command Secondary School at Efa. The well-known Qua Iboe Church, seconded to the Qua Iboe Church Ibeno, was established in 1894 by Samuel Bill and is the reason Etinan is famous. Since this region of Africa was under colonial rule, the church has played a significant role in the socioeconomic, political, and educational benefits that the people of Etinan enjoy. The Qua Iboe Church Printing Press is still recognised in history as the earliest printing press in all of West Africa. Etinan Local Government Area hosted additional Christian churches today.

On the moral values of the people of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, the people are culturally known for hospitality and respect. And these moral attributes are transferred from one generation to another. Young ones are taught to respect

elders, and greet elders first in all occasions. Boys are taught to respect girls and women as women are as the earth and water to humanity and life to living things. Young people are taught to respect and obey their parents. Iman Ibom community is considered as the arena for breeding good and respectful young people who believe in dignity of labour and truth. The Iman Ibom Clan has a belief system that the young shall grow to be elder someday and must be able to live a good modelled life as he or she grows, by respecting others and not taking what does not belong to him or her. These and many more are built in the Iman Ibom cultural life patterns.

3.3 Population of the Study

A total of 89,907 men and 79,377 women made up the 215,600 people living in the Etinan Local Government Area according to the results of the 2006 population census (NPC, 2006). The predicted population of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area by 2022 was 252, 312 people, including men and women, based on the 2006 census result indices, according to the Akwa Ibom State Demographic Profile (2018).

3.4 Sample and Sampling Technique

A multi-level sampling technique was used in the study. Iman Ibom people who ranged in age from 18 years and above to form the basis for key informants participants were purposively selected from Iman North and Iman South in the Etinan Local Government Area using the big-net technique (Fatterman, 2010). The researcher utilised the big-net approach to randomly choose the actual study participants (Fatterman, 2010). In the first stage of the sampling, the clan was divided into 2 (Iman North and Iman South) according to the current geopolitical divisions. The clusters of Iman North and Iman South were therefore considered for the selection of study participants. A total of 4 villages were purposively selected based on their similar features regarding the high youth population,

drug and alcohol abuse, crime prevalence, and presence of communal conflicts. The study participants were then chosen on a random basis using a straightforward procedure in each of the chosen villages to ensure the elimination of bias and allow anybody within the chosen age cohort to be part of the study.

3.5 Data Collection Technique

The investigator utilised a big-net strategy (Fetterman, 2010) to ascertain the study sample and collect data from the research participants. Through in-depth, in-person interviews with participants, these primary sources provided the data for this scientific investigation. In addition to conducting in-depth interviews, the study included additional techniques for gathering data. These include key informant interview communication with the elderly residents of Etinan Local Government Area for participatory appraisal, informal discussion, in-depth interview, and participant observation.

- i. **Participant Observation:** Fetterman (2010) states that participant observation is essential to successful fieldwork and is a defining feature of most ethnographic research. Participant observation is absorption in a culture that involves taking part in the life of the subjects of the study while maintaining a professional distance that permits sufficient observation and data recording (Fetterman, 2010). Participant observers frequently engage in the day-to-day operations of the culture they are studying. The researcher engaged participant observation by objectively taking part in the cultural activities of the people as demanded by anthropological fieldwork.
- ii. **Interview:** With the assistance of a few assistants, the researcher conducted interviews to ensure that all participants were covered within the time frame for the fieldwork. The interviewers were expected to provide candid and objective replies to the questions that made up the interview schedule. The interview schedule's Section A looked at the participants' socio-demographic details, whereas Section B

concentrated on the substantive problems that the study's objectives had uncovered.

The interview schedule contained open-ended questions which the researcher and his field assistants asked the study participants.

- iii. **Key Informant Discussion:** The researcher enlisted the help of key informants, from each cluster of the study area, to help with data collection for the study. To provide clarification on cultural concerns about drug, alcohol, and illicit substance acceptance, usage, and abuse, one elder (community leader) from each cluster was selected.

3.6 Procedure for Data Collection

Two (2) research assistants were acquired, trained and well-equipped for data collection purposes. In the situation where the study participants didn't understand the English language, the vernacular was used by the researcher and his assistants for data collection in this investigation. In the case of the situation stated earlier, the interview schedule's English language questions were directly translated into the expected vernacular. Notes were taken accordingly. To facilitate simple coding and data processing, the information taken in the vernacular was later translated into English.

3.7 Instrumentation

The instrument was designed with open-ended questions to allow study participants to provide information without feeling compelled to react in a certain way. The questions were designed to elicit the study participant's socio-demographic details as well as the participants' honest opinions of the study's goals on substantive issues. During the interviews, questions were translated into vernacular where necessary.

3.8 Validity of Instruments

The researcher ensured that the data collection tool designed for this study was subjected to meticulous scrutiny and examination. Experts in qualitative data analysis and ethnographic research were expected to make corrections and offer inputs by removing questions that had nothing to do with the study's goals. The interview schedule was rearranged to satisfy the professional guidelines for anthropological studies and to meet the standards for legitimate qualitative research, as well as the need to improve efficient data collection for the study's aims.

3.9 Reliability of Instrument

The researcher took care to ensure that the instrument to be used in the study met the required standards for reliability for data collection for the study and had been thoroughly vetted by experts in the field of anthropological studies. The reliability was conducted through a test–re-test during a pilot study that was conducted by the researcher.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

A table of percentage distribution was used for the presentation and the descriptive analysis of data on the study participants' socio-demographic characteristics. Since the study was exploratory in design, competing raw narratives were analysed thematically utilising verbatim report excerpts, arranged systematically to address substantial questions captured in the interview schedule.

3.11 Limitation of the Study

Some limitations were encountered by the researcher during the fieldwork and were later worked to successfully overcome. One of the challenges was the issue of the rain which the researcher had to give more time than what was expected of the researcher for

the study. Another was the rising cost of goods and services which brought about changes in the researcher's budget for the study. The attitude of the study participants were such as was expected of the researcher and his field assistants, as the youths were initially posing serious reluctant attitude to be part of the study unless they were financially compensated by the researcher. The researcher took more time to close social distance through some forms of informal discussions to bring the study participants to the level of understanding that the research was purely for academic purposes.

3.12 Ethical Issues

To adhere to ethical standards, the researcher obtained the participants' agreement and provided them with the flexibility to engage in the study as well as the option to stop at any time. The researcher provided the study participants in the study with sufficient assurances regarding their privacy. The investigator made sure that appropriate study protocols were implemented for the above-mentioned data collection and analysis.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 4.1: Socio-Demographics of Respondents

Demographic profile	Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Female	228	57.0
	Male	172	43.0
Age of Respondent	18-25yrs	56	14.0
	26-33yrs	62	15.50
	34-41yrs	130	32.50
	42-49yrs	102	25.50
	50 and above	50	12.50
Educational Status	No Formal Education	23	5.75
	Primary Education	133	33.25
	Secondary Education	175	43.75
	Tertiary Education	69	17.25
Marital Status	Single	52	13.0
	Married	211	52.8
	Divorced	43	10.7
	Widow	83	20.8
	Separated	11	2.7
Religion	Christian	361	90.25
	Traditional Religion	19	4.75
	Muslim	5	1.25
	Others	15	3.75
Occupation	Civil Servant	132	33.0
	Trader	223	55.8
	Artisan	17	4.2
	Unemployed	28	7.0

Source: Peters, (2024).

The socio-demographic distribution of the sampled participants as shown in Table 4.1, implies that the number of the participants was 400, the females constituted of 228 (57%) while the male constituted 172 (43%) male. The gender percentage show that the views of the study respondents expressed in this study are representative of both male and female, with the female study participants being majority.

Table 4.1 also shows that within the age characteristics, the majority of the study respondents (130/32.5%) were between ages 34 - 41 years. This is followed by age 42 -49 years (102/25.5%), 62 (15.5%) of the study respondents were 26 - 33years of age, 56 (14%) were between the ages of 18 – 25 years, and 50 (12.5%) were 50 years and above. This implies that majority of the study respondents were of the younger age group of the study population's sample. Study respondents gave information as related to the main theme of this scientific investigation and made meaningful contribution in line with the objectives of the study.

Under the educational status of the study respondents, those without any formal education were 23(5.75%), those with formal education in the primary level were 133(33.25%), those having attended secondary level of education were 175(43.75%), and those with tertiary education were 69(17.25%). This implies that the study respondents with secondary level of education (SSCE) were the majority of the sampled participants. This was followed by those with primary level of education (FLSC), and those with tertiary level of education (NCE, ND, HND, BSC, and others) were the next while, those with no formal education were the least in terms of sampled size of the study respondents.

It is also observed that under the marital status category, the highest is the married with 211 (52.8%) of the study participants, this is followed by the widow/widowers with 83 (20.8%). The next in this category is singles with 52 (13.0%), while 43 (10.7%) were divorced, and the least in this category is the separated with 11 (2.7%). A great proportion of the study participants were married, while the least proportion of the population's sample was that of the separated. Under the religious affiliation, the result of Table 4.1 shows that 361 (90.25%) of the study participants were Christians, 19 (4.75%) were traditional worshipers, 5(1.25%) of the study participants were Muslims, while 15 (3.75 %) were into another form of religious practices. Christians were the majority of the study respondents in terms of religious affiliation. Under the occupation category, traders were

the highest proportion of the study respondents with 223 (55.8%), followed by civil servants with 132 (33%). unemployed were 28 (7.0%) and the least in this category is artisans with 17 (4.2%). The analysis of the occupation category shows that majority of the study respondents are producers of local crafts. The indication of this is that the study participants covered large proportion of the socio-demographic characteristics. This was necessary for obtaining unbiased opinions from study participants on the main subject of study across the study area.

4.2 Findings

Culture of alcohol and drug abuse enhances distorted values

Traditional practices have created cultural avenues for psychoactive drug abuse among the youths of Etinan local Government Area. Participants emphasized the role of list content of traditional marriage requirement as key cultural provisions for alcoholic and psychoactive substance abuse among the Iman Ibom youths in Etinan Local Government Area. They agreed that there are such items like illicit gin, schnapps, different brands of hot drink, dry tobacco leaves, grinded snuff, beer of different brands, palm wine, and penetrol cannot be excluded from the traditional marriage requirement list for any reasons what so ever.

One of the Key Informants participants aged 57 years explained:

There are some items you cannot take out of our traditional marriage requirement list. If you do, then it is no longer Etinan traditional marriage requirement list. Let me tell you, presenting traditional marriage list without those items will look as if you are a stranger to our customs. Those items like illicit gin, palm wine, tobacco, snuff, hot drinks, and beer, are what make the marital requirement list traditional and celebrative. This is because, everything other items like the cloths and bride price belong to the parents, but these other items are what the parents do share with the people and youths also have their own share. Therefore, if the youths abuse their own share which is what we have observed these days, that is their own issues and I know

that they now know what the consequences are (Male, 57years, interviewed on 04/6/2024).

As part of observation and interview, the youths are given a special section of the traditional marriage requirement with items that are capable of intoxicating them. It was gathered by the researcher that there is a part of the traditional marriage requirement list which is referred to as “NkpoIwaad” otherwise translated as “Youths’ Items”. This section of the list contains items like cigarettes of different brands, grinded snuff (tobacco), kolanut, illicit gin, hot drink, beer, palm wine, and other items. The youths have over the years and generations, collected such items as the part of their requirement for giving out one of their own out in marriage.

One of the study participants from focus group discussion aged 47 years revealed that these items or sections of the list is very important if at all anyone wants to marry from any family in Etinan Local Government Area:

Youths’ items is an important part of the list. This is so because, if the groom’s family does not pay everything as contain in the list either before the day of the traditional marriage or on the arrival of the groom’s family for the traditional marriage, the youths of that community will come out and block the entrance to the bride’s family compound against the groom and his family on the marriage day. The youths have since been involved in the consumption of these items as morally accepted items (Female, 54 years, interviewed on 04/7/2024).

Discussion on burial rites and drug abuse revealed that there are many aspects of burial ceremonies of Iman Ibom people which include “ntord” (reporting to different parties which include; siblings, in-laws, immediate family, major/extended family, and the village as the case may demands), “ubede ufok ikpo” (opening of funeral home), “ubob ndak” (building of traditional tent), “Ubo nkpo” (collection of levy), “usuan ufok ikpo” (closing of funeral home) and “ukpok ndak” (losing and scattering of traditional tent).

These sub-cultural complexes of Iman Ibom people burial rites according to gathered information through interview, unveil the cultural practices promote alcohol and tobacco and other psychoactive substances consumption. Study participants explained that illicit gin, palm wine, beer, tobacco, hot drinks and other items are collected through assessment list from in-laws and relatives. In other cases, these items are bought for consumption by the bereaved family through assessment money from immediate relatives or family members.

A participant aged 42 years explained in his narratives how alcohol and psychoactive substances are collected and shared among the people during burial ceremonies. According to him:

In our community we collect illicit gin, palm wine, hot drinks and other food items from our in-laws and other relatives through what we call assessment. These items are used for entertainment during the burial rites. These items are consumed by our people according to the cultural grouping of people during the burial ceremonies. The youths (iwaad) are always given their special place and entertained with items like beer, illicit gin, hot drink, palm wine, and food items. This is tradition which is carried out all over Iman Ibom is customized to be right by our forefathers, and there is nothing wrong with it (Uk, male, 42 years, interviewed 02/7/2024).

Traditional marriage ceremonies have been a custom among Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area as a grand celebration of giving out Iman Ibom daughter out in marriage by the family concern. Study participants explained that traditional marriage ceremony can be in-door or out-door depending on the financial capacity of the groom and the groom's family. During burial ceremonies in Etinan Local Government Area, Iman Ibom people performed several burial rites which according to the study participants include "ububndak" (building of traditional tent). From observation and discussion, this particular burial rite traditionally takes place 2 days or a day to the burial

ceremony. By observation, this has served as an opportunity for youths to abuse alcohol and psychoactive substances.

Information gathered through key informant interview revealed that there are cultural practices of the people of Etinan Local Government Area which have been modified especially by the pressure of the youths in order to expand the moral boundary created by traditional practices for their selfish interest. These youths have built on the cultural acceptability of alcoholic and other psychoactive substances within the context of traditional rites to introduce other substances and increase the number of traditional items that are to be collected or given to the youths during traditional events.

Like in the case of “ubub ndak” (building of traditional tent) as burial rites, the community leader as one of the Key Informants had this to say:

This ubub ndak was a tradition of our people in those days when there was nothing like canopies and tents for rent as we have today. I remember when I was a child, our fathers did not have formalin to embalm their dead, so they would keep the dead body standing at the corner of the room, pour a bottle of original illicit gin, not the chemical they drink today oh, into the dead body through the mouth and closed the mouth thereafter. The body will stay for 3 – 4 days without decay. This is when family and community members will come for ubub ndak (Male 75 years, interviewed on 07/07/2024).

The participant went on to say that;

This traditional tent was to create a shed against the sun or reduce the pressure of rainwater during the burial ceremony. It was traditionally customized that the bereaved family would bring food and drinks that they could afford but today, the youths have come out with list of items they must collect for ubub ndak and this include all these substances that make them high so that they can work very well according to them. I have been mobilizing for the abolition of ubub ndak in my

community, but the youths are also mobilizing against my motion on this which is why I say that the youths are no more respectful of the elders especially when they drink these substances. They will begin to insult people and if control is not enforce by God's grace, sometimes they quarrel among themselves or with the elders (Male 75 years, interviewed on 07/07/2024).

On "ukpokndak" (scattering or pulling down of the traditional tent), the tradition is facing elimination in some parts of Northern Iman region of Etinan Local Government Area as some elders in the most communities are mobilizing against the abuse of the practices by the community youths. This tradition according to discussion has it that after the burial ceremony, a day will be set aside by the bereaved family for the family and community to come and pull down or scatter the traditional tent. This cultural practice is accompanied with presentation of food and alcoholic drinks (like illicit gin, beer, hot drinks). Information gotten through interview revealed that the youths have seized the opportunity to make demands outside what was culturally accepted there shifting the acceptable boundaries and using such avenues to showcase conflictual social behaviours which were not morally prescribed by the elders.

According to the key informant;

Ukpok ndak should be abolished among my people. This is my stand. I have said it again and again. My stand is because the youths have used this practice to make unnecessary demands for items that are beyond our moral standards. You cannot come to "ukpok ndak" with marijuana in our fathers' days. But today, they will come with marijuana, demand cigarettes, look for how they can mix these psychoactive leaves with kai kai (illicit gin), and at the end, they will be overly high and start insulting their elders in any little case. So I influenced the dismantling of the tent immediately after the burial on the same day with only a bottle of kai kai and I am still

pushing on with it. By God's grace we will abolish that practice
(Male, 70 years, interviewed on 29/6/2024).

The people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State have culturally prescribed codes and traditional rites of passage for youths. These have defined what is accepted by the society and what is not accepted. The provision of psychoactive substances for youths as traditional requirements for traditional rites as part of the culture of the people has created avenues for the youths to abuse psychoactive substances and drugs during traditional activities and as part of normal youthful life by some youths. Gathered data have shown that the youths have seized such traditional rights to force expansion of culture boundaries for inclusion of other substances which some are traditionally produced with local herbs and under such anti-social behaviour, the youths have become deviants in society.

The influence of some cultural practices on the lives of the youths as gathered by the researchers is in the creation of avenues for psychoactive drug abuse. Most of the youths are looking for any available avenue created by cultural events where drinks and foods are shared for them to seize it as an opportunity to consume alcohol and psychoactive substances and drugs. Gathered information through observations and interviews revealed that most of the youths in Etinan Local Government Area see traditional rites items which include alcohol, raw tobacco, petrol, cigarettes, snuff, and other illicit substances as the license for abuse of psychoactive substances and distortion of cultural values. Participants of the study through interview agreed that most of the youths of Etinan Local Government Area have used the provisions of traditional rights as a measure for consuming psychoactive substances which according to gathered data are responsible for the anti-social behaviour which the youths are living today.

One of the study participants during the interview said that;

Most of our youths have no respect for elders today as a result
of what they are taking which are these ikpoo and other things

that make them high. You will see a young boy of 13 years behaving and talking to his senior with disrespect as if he is as old as the person he is talking to. This is because when they talk about those things, they see everybody as equal and they will insult their elders. This is not how we used to live while we were young in our days. We were taught respect and honor to the elders and our seniors. In our days, you dare not touch what does not belong to you. But today, these small boys do not consider these morals again. They have decided to wreck our society because of the things they smoke and drink. And you can't blame them because it is the elders that accepted those "mkpomkparawa" for them which are all illicit and can control their brain. I pray God helps us with our upcoming children otherwise, I have fear for what our society will be like in the future (Male, 49 years old, interviewed on 02/07/ 2024).

Gathered information through interviews and observation has shown that the community life among the people of Etinan Local Government Area is facing a serious shift from what was formerly known and considered to be driven by good cultural value to what is today seen as anti-value or distorted value lifestyles by the youths due to the influence of psychoactive substances and drug abuse by some youths of the local government area. Youths have through the influence of psychoactive drug and substance abuse deviated from the socially accepted moral codes of conduct and practices.

One of the participants in her responses reported that;

These substances that our youths take these days have done us much evil because we are losing our children and the crime rate seems to be increasing within our homes. We now have children who talk back to their parents, some even fight their parents, some will even curse and abuse their parents, and some are even fighting among themselves as siblings with cutlasses. Some fought until they destroyed what was supposed to be their inheritance from their father. What is the

cause? These things that they smoke and drink every day which we did not see or use these kind things during our days. But now, a girl is not a girl, you will see them form gangs and share these items among themselves. When these things start to hit them, they will begin to cause trouble even for their family. It is a pity that the world has spoiled and children are no more children again. Today you see them do things that when we were of their age we couldn't do such things. But these things are making high and they misbehave (Female, 52 years interviewed on 24/06/2024)

Another study participant as a youth said that:

We should know that the world has changed and we are no more in those old school days. Everything has changed and we have to change along. Sir, if you don't change along the world will leave you behind. We are not taking things that the elders are not talking about. We are learning from them. Sir, let me tell you, you do not know what those leaders take but they will not want us to take. Why? We are human beings too and our blood is even stronger than their own. But when you see us make trouble, it is because the elders want to rob us of our rights and we want to enforce our rights so that they will not cheat us (Male, 26 years, interviewed on 02/07/2024)

Values are prescribe by culture and traditional rites are mediums through which culture are code, preserved and transfer from one generation to another. These values are prescribed by the elders of the society as custodians of customs and traditions. When the elders prescribed psychoactive substances for the youths as traditional rights, the youths as found among the people of Iman Ibom in Etinan Local Government Area through interviews revealed that most youths through the influence of psychoactive substances have changed and falsified the cultural value of the people of Etinan Local Government Area.

Culture of Alcohol and drug abuse and the formation of the cycle of alcohol and drug abuse and addiction

Emergence from gathered data through narratives of the study participants shown that there are cultural practices of the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State which have been in existence as long as the existence of the people. Data show that these cultural practices have been preserved as traditions of Iman Ibom people and transferred from one generation to the other. According to the study participants, these practices are avenues of abusing alcohol and psychoactive substances. The preservation of these cultural practices like traditional marriage ceremony, burial rites, *ubud nkad*, *ukpok ndak*, *uno mkpo* (collection of levy or traditional list) has form pattern of alcohol and drug abuse among Iman Ibom youths. A study participant in her narrative, reported that;

I don't know how we started this thing that is becoming a serious problem for our youths today. The concern is that it is affecting everybody because if there is for instant a burial event or traditional marriage event, you will see this youth come out in good numbers to make demands of their items and these items contain alcohol and other things that make them high. They will threaten to cause problem if these items are not given to them. They will claim that it is their right as tradition, that tradition is tradition and there is no amendment. So, the people will have to give them what they want so that they can do their event in peace. You can see that these traditional practices in becoming a serious issue among us because the youths have seize it for abuse of alcohol and other things (Female, 35 years, interviewed on 05/07/2024)

Another study participant in the study reported through narratives that;

These traditional practices have become cycles of consumption and abuse of alcohol and psychoactive substances among the youths and the elders in Iman.what I mean is that, those who are elders today are already in the abuse because they have been addicted to alcohol and these substances like tobacco, cigarettes, and today the youths collect what they call combine which is a mixture of marijuana and ethanol (kai kai) through continual usage because they sit at every traditional event to collect these items for the youths and for the elders. So, you can imagine when a young man of 15 years starts drink alcohol and smokes as part of traditions with other youths and he does that year in year out until he become adult and join the elders group. At this point, he has been in the cue of consumption and later abuse throughout his youthful life to elders' class. So, you can see the cycle is formed already (Male, 68 years, interviewed on 27/06/2024)

The abuse of alcohol and drugs among Iman Ibom youths was discovered through gathered data as a cultural practices. According to narratives from interviews, participants reported that alcohol and drug abuse have become some families cultural practices in Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. A study participant in her narrated that;

We have witnessed many families live in the abuse of alcohol and smoking of marijuana and cigarettes. Some their fathers are late today and the children cannot learn from what killed their father. Some, the abuse of alcohol killed their father through liver problem and killed the first son through liver problem and the second son is still in the business of abusing alcohol especially as a leader of a youth group. You see, when a father was a youth and collected youths' items and drink and smoke until he become elder. As an elder he collect for his children who youths and the children join him in the abuse of alcohol and smoking. The thing is that today, the children are even

smoking what he the father did not smoke in his days and drink what the father did not drink in his days. The practices though it is tradition become a family sickness of abuse, like from father to children and the children will grow in the abuse (Female, 40 years, interviewed on 17/5/2024).

Gathered data have also revealed that Iman Ibom youths are conscious of the cycle of abuse sometimes, they make case for it. During interviews, participants express wariness in the knowledge of the cycle by the youths who in traditional event work to enforced the cycle as part of the conventional practices of Iman Ibom people. Culture is learned, as the youths learned through the process of collecting youths items as part of traditional practices in the culture of Iman Ibom people, they get acquainted with the cycle and the changes within the cycle which occur at the point of passage from the youth age cohort to that of the elder. According to study participants, youths have often made it openly known to their elders that it is their turn to collect and consume what the elders used to collect while they were youths. One of the study participants in her narrative reported that;

These youths are really into consuming alcohol excessively in such a level that sometimes get me worried. I don't know if it is because of the economic hardship. The most important part of this is that these youths see that it is their turn to collect and consume. So, they will challenge the elders if the elders want to amend what should be given to them. You will hear them say something like; Obong owo give us our drinks and smoke because you cannot rob us of our turn. When it was your turn, you used to collect and smoke now you want to stop us. If you try it you will see our wrath and nobody will seat here. Then the elders will have to allow them have their take (Male, 65 years, interviewed on 13/04/2024)

Another study participant in her report stated that;

This alcohol abuse and addiction thing has become *Mkpo Ufok* (family issue). It has been a cycle form within some family and this cycle keep on recycling from one generation to the other because they feel it is tradition and tradition cannot be amended and the even when some of the fathers who were into abuse in their youthful days but God help them out now want to modify the youths' item, the majority of the youths do not agree and they have even introduce new substances to be collected and abuse as part of youths' items (Male, 48 years, interviewed on 15/03/2024)

The culture of alcohol and drug consumption among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area has brought about the creation of cycle of alcohol and drug abuse among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan. The traditional practices of traditional marriage ceremony, burial rites, *ubud nkad*, *ukpok ndak*, *uno mkpo* (collection of levy or traditional list), coronation of chiefs, village meetings, family meetings, consultations of village council, consultation of youths for political events and other cultural practices are the pattern of cycle of alcohol and drugs abuse among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. According to gathered data, the Iman Ibom youths have sized their opportunities created for them by the traditional practices to abuse alcohol and other psychoactive substances which become a cycle that is preserved in the practices and transfer from one generation to the other.

Perceptions of the roles of “mkpomkparawa” as the pattern of alcohol and drug abuse

The abuse of alcohol and drugs among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan according to gathered data has been traced to the cultural practices of recognizing the youths as core structure of the Iman Ibom society with special allocated items in every traditional event. This items according to the study participants are found to be sacrosanct for the young age cohort who are believed to be the pillars of the land. This special allocated items to the

youths are referred to as “*Mkpomkparawa*”. Narratives from interviews have shown that *mkpomkparawa* (youths’ items) are sentenced as tradition which must be performed in every traditional even among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. One of the study participants in her narratives reported that;

Mkpomkparawa is a list of items that you have to give to the youths as tradition. It is something that everybody knows and it is what everybody must give if you want to do any traditional event in Iman Ibom. It is something that nobody can run away from only you do not have any traditional event to do (Female, 38 years, interviewed on 19/06/2024).

Gathered data from interviews have shown that the majority of the study participants agreed in their narratives that *mkpomkparawa* has become a cycle for breeding alcohol abusers and drug addicts among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. According to one of the study participants, *Mkpomkparawa* has become an instrument for creation of cycle of consumption and abuse of alcohol from one generation to the other. In her narrative, she reported that;

We were born to see the existence of *mkpomkpara* as up till now *mkpomkparawa* is still here and I don’t see it being erased from the culture of my people because the youths has understanding of what it means for them. The point here is that this so call *mkpomkparawa* has being a cycle for consumption and abuse of alcohol and other drugs among the youths here (Female, 50 years, interviewed on 13/05/2024).

The youths in Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area are using *mkpomkparawa* as medium to enforce their demands for consumption and abuse of alcohol and drugs. They build on the traditional order of give youths psychoactive substance

because a cultural precept to consider youthful age as the age cohort for energy and hard work which in the cultural order demands something that is psychoactive to suit the personalities of the age cohort. During interviews, narratives show that the youths are traditionally comfortable with mkpomkparawa as a medium for demands for the consumption and abuse of alcohol, drugs, and other substances.

One of the study participants narrated that;

The present-day youths are forcing for more through mkpomkparawa as a medium to collect items like kai kai, palmwine, beer, cigarettes, dry tobacco leaves, snuff, penetrol, and presently they are forcing for inclusion of marijuana either in physical wraps or a mixture of it with kai kai. When marijuana is not included for them, they bring it to the event centre and start smoking because mkpomkparawa has already given them the opportunity for tobacco smoking (Male, 48 years old, interviewed on 15/06/2024).

Another participant in his narrative reported that;

We were indeed born to meet these traditions and we say that tradition is tradition. Meaning we cannot change because it was laid down for us by our fathers as it is done in other places especially across the Iman Ibom land.... It is true that we collect items like alcohol, cigarettes, tobacco and local gin for the youths as “Mkpomkparawa” which is common among Iman Ibom people but, I am of concern that this tradition has open up our young ones for drugs and substance abuse and addictions (Male, 50 years old, interviewed on 12/12/2023).

The traditional practices of Iman Ibom people over time have witnessed the key roles and functions of the traditional code known and call mkpomkparawa. Gathered data

have revealed that mkpomkparawa has served as a traditional code for preservation and transfer of alcohol and drug abuse from one generation to the other. According to a study participant, mkpomkparawa is more of an unknown evil among the Iman Ibom people that is taking away the future leaders of the Iman Ibom society while creating problems among the people through the youths who in their addiction will cause more of harm than good from their family units to the communities at large. In her words, she stated that:

This mkpomkparawa is an evil that is celebrated by our people for the youths. It is like a masquerade that looks different in the outside but the real carrier of the masquerade is different from the masquerade itself. What mkpomkparawa is doing to our youths is quite different from what the people thinks or may be know about. This thing has created alcohol and drug addicts among our youths. It has caused many deaths among us because when a son becomes addicted to alcohol and drugs like we have witnessed here in Etinan, he keep stealing from the parents and some forced their parent to give them money for alcohol and drugs to the extent of forcefully take the parent ATM card for withdrawal which later led to the shock and sudden death of the parent. So, this thing call mkpomkparwa is an evil in the bosom of our community (Female, 42 years old, interviewed on 27/12/23)

Another study participant reported that;

My dear, you will see families of drunks and drug addicts today in this community and in some cases they have become nuisance to others and to the community. This is all because this mkpomkparawa is the route to addiction and transfer of addiction in these families. The father was once a youth and got addicted by partaking in mkpomkparawa. Now, the children are

youths and are swimming in mkpomkparawa, and they are already addicts. So, we have families of alcohol and drug addicts among us because of mkpomkparawa (Female, 62 years old, interviewed on 03/01/2024).

The roles of mkpomkparawa among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area ranges from creation of patterns and cycle of alcohol and drug abuse, cycle of addiction, traditional code for preservation of alcohol and drug abuse, transfer of alcohol and drug consumption and abuse from one generation to the other, medium of collection of alcohol and psychoactive substances, to cycle of family tradition of alcohol and drug abuse. These are deducted from narratives through interviews as gathered data on the Iman Ibom people perceptions on mkpomkparawa among the Iman Ibom youths.

Culture of alcohol and drug abuse, and criminal behaviours

Emergence from the study as gathered by the researcher show that there exist traditional rites among the Iman Ibom people that are legal patterns for alcohol, tobacco and other psychoactive substance consumption and abuse. These traditional rites form generational pattern of substance abuse among the Iman Ibom youths. According to findings by the researcher through interviews, discussions and observations, these include; traditional marriage rites, which the people of Iman Ibom origin collect alcoholic drinks of different type/brands and other psychoactive substances as part of their requirement for giving out their daughters in marriage. Study participants and family heads engaged as key informants in the study explained that it is a laid down tradition by their fathers to collect alcoholic and psychoactive substances as part of their marital requirement in giving out their daughters in marriage. Therefore, they cannot change a practice that has existed over the generations and it is acceptable by everybody

According to one of the study participants;

See, our tradition is tradition, we did not create them but it was handed over to us by our fathers who also took over from their fathers; that alcoholic drinks and those other items whether it is intoxicated or psychoactive substances must be collected as part of traditional marriage requirements for giving out our daughters. That is why we do stress the point Traditional Marriage Requirements so that one will know that it a tradition, not something we just sit down and say okay let us collect this or that. It is in inherited and transmitted from one generation to another. (Male, 57 years old, interviewed on 20/2/2024).

According to another participant, a community leader in Etinan Local Government Area, narrated that:

What you see today as traditional marriage requirement list is not what was obtainable as our traditional marriage requirement. Our children today have borrowed a lot of things into our cultural practices. This may be because they have a lot of people to entertain today than those days. We didn't use to collect beer, penetrol, cigarette, and hot drinks, but dry tobacco, grinded snuff, kola nut, original illicit gin and palm wine were what we used to collect. Beer, hot drink and penetrol were introduced to our people by the British. Today our people are collecting these alcoholic drinks in quantities that is alarming, and sometime I do asked some of my people if they want to open a drink shop after their daughters' marriage, but it will surprised you that our people will finish these drinks and cigarettes, and add more to it (Male, 70 years old, interviewed on 20/1/2024).

Traditional marriage rites was viewed as offering opportunity for Iman Ibom youths to abuse alcohol and psychoactive substances under the guide of observing cultural practices during marriage ceremonies through the presentation of items for youths called “mkpomkparawa” or youths items which is a must give requirement that contain alcohol drinks, tobacco and other substances.

Findings of the study during interviews, observations, key informants, and informal discussions show that alcohol and psychoactive substance abuse by Iman Ibom youths at the occasion of traditional rites ceremonies have not only form patterns of drug abuse, but have created substance abuse addictions among the youths and by extension increase the tendency to indulge in deviant behaviours. According to findings, most Iman Ibom youths have become addicted of alcohol, tobacco, cigarettes, marijuana, and other drugs through participations in traditional rites ceremonies. One of the study his responses said that:

If you go to where there is a traditional marriage ceremony or burial ceremony, you will see a lot of youths there trying to struggle for alcohol and other psychoactive things and most times, some of them bring other items and drugs to sell to their friends at the venue because they know that, that is where they have cultural right to smoke, drink and eat anything that is given to them as youths. So I have concern on these things because after they finish taking these things, you become aggressive and most times they indulge in criminal acts (Male, 50 years old, interviewed on 12/12/ 2023).

Further findings of the study show that Iman Ibom youths engage in criminal behaviours under the influence of alcohol and other psychoactive substances. According to findings from study participants, the majority of the youths who engage in criminal behaviours like rape, stealing, thuggery, assaults and other violence behaviour are said to

do so under the influence of alcohol and smoking of marijuana. One of the study participants in her responses reported that:

Most of these youths are behaving like criminals; in fact, a lot of them are criminals today. I don't blame them, it is just that the elders, those who supposed to tell them not to take some kind things that will make them high, are the one enforcing that such things should be given to them during occasions in order to calm the youths from making trouble because they will disturb the event and from there may steal or loot away your things as criminals. Every time people have events especially traditional events these days, you must have security for your event to hold successfully and peacefully. Else, these youths after they have smoke their weed and drink all manners of mix alcohol, they will cause problem in order to have chance to steal and loot away people properties. And you should know that where the host has as a son who is something among the youths, eh, eh, eh, that one, the person must prepare their stuff complete else there will be serious problems and they will use the opportunity to steal, loots and assault somebody (Female, 62 years old, interviewed on 19/9/2023)

Another study participant had this to say:

You see this alcohol and smoking of weed during traditional events, it has caused so many bad things and bad behaviour within our community. There is one married lady that used to drink at burial and traditional ceremony and she will always get drunk. There was one of the burial nights' vigil that she drank and got drunk. So without her knowledge under the influence of the alcohol, young boys under the

influence of weed and brew helped her into a room for her to rest there, and only for her to wake up later and discovered that her pant was not on her and she has been raped and raped. So these things have been responsible for many criminal behaviours among our youths (Female, 50 years old, interviewed on 16/12/2023)

Substance abuse during traditional rites has been found to be responsible for so many criminal behaviours among the Iman Ibom youths. A study participants interviewed during one of the traditional burial rites in Etinan, in his responses narrated how they used to drugged drinks and rice for young girls to eat and drink during events in other to have their consciousness knocked-off so that the boys can have unsolicited sex with the girls. According to him:

You see these girls will think that they are strong such that sometimes they want to compete with guys. But some of them are very stubborn and sometimes we use what we known to win them. Sometimes we will have to mix drinks like weed with kaikai and Alomo Bitter for those girls, if the thing does not overcome them, we take them home and cook rice with pepper soup and used more weed (Marijuana) in the pepper soup for them and that one will get them off and get their pants away and more fucking men (Male, 54 years old, interviewed on 27/12/2023)

Iman Ibom youth by findings are found to engage in criminal behaviours under the influence of alcohol and drug abuse. Traditional rites have been responsible for the substance abuse by Iman Ibom youths and such have been found to be responsible for most criminal behaviours found among the youths. Youths through findings were into criminal behaviours under the influence of alcohol and substance abuse.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Emerging findings from interviews, observations, discussions and key informants reports show that alcohol and substance abuse is rooted in the traditional rites of the Iman Ibom people in Akwa Ibom State. Jiloha (2009) gives credence to this finding postulating that drug abuse is a multifaceted phenomenon with various social, economic, cultural, geographical, biological and historical aspects. This finding revealed that alcohol and drug abuse is traditional among the Iman Ibom youths of Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State and it is culturally cultivated in the cultural tenets of their traditional practices. This finding gives credence to Usoro *et al.*, (2017), and Peters and Bassey (2020). It was found that traditional marriage rite and burial rites are among others, some of the traditional rites with allocated rights of alcohol and substance consumption for the Iman Ibom youths. On abuse and addiction of substances, findings show that youths consider traditional rites as opportunities for alcohol and substance abuse which later lead to abuse. Abuse of alcohol and substance among Iman Ibom youths were found to be a follow-up behaviour from substance consumption during traditional marriage and burial rites. The abuse is an act of continuity in taking stimulant substances which have high tendencies of causing addiction especially among young people.

Emerging from the findings of the study is that cultural practices like traditional marriage ceremony and burial ceremony create avenue for psychoactive substance abuse among the Iman Ibom youths of Etinan Local Government Area. Findings of the study show that traditional marriage requirement list plays a pivotal point in the traditional marriage ceremony among the people of Etinan Local Government Area. The researcher discovered through findings that alcohol and psychoactive substances like tobacco, cigarettes, and petrol are contained in the traditional marriage list for Iman Ibom youths in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Nwagu (2017) gives credence to the findings from this study when he reported that there are local cultural norms that are central

factors and can influence the use of alcohol and other psychoactive substances. It was further noted that collection of these psychoactive substances as part of traditional marriage requirements in giving out their daughters in marriage, is regarded as tradition which had been laid down by their ancestors, and had been upheld from generation to generations. Further findings show that the youths found the cultural acceptability of these psychoactive substances by their fathers as moral licence to drink and abuse alcohol, smoke cigarettes, consume marijuana, inhale tobacco in form of snuff, and produce new psychoactive liquor called “brew” (a mixture of kaikai, palm wine, marijuana, tramadol, lemon grass, and hollandia yogurt).

Findings of the study also revealed that burial rites are performed along with alcohol and psychoactive substances by the people of Iman Ibom clan, in Etinan Local Government Area. Findings on burial ceremony show that the youths (mkparawa) are greatly involved in the burial activities and have influenced the items which they must be given as “Mkpomkparawa” (youths’ items). These items according to findings contain alcohol and other psychoactive substances which are traditionally accepted and as the custom of the people to give such items to the youths during burial rite such as in “ububndak” (building of traditional tent), “ukpokndak” (dismantling or pulling down of the traditional tent), and on the burial day. Dumbili (2013) give credence to the findings when argued that in Nigeria, alcohol usage and abuse have a standing history among the youths especially where alcohol is not forbidden by religion. Alcohol is used as part of traditional rituals, funerals, burials and marriage ceremonies. The use of alcoholic drinks has been an integral factor of cultures for many years across various nations (McGovern, 2009).

Emergence of the study further revealed that there are cultural practices of the people of Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area which have been modified especially by the pressure of the youths in order to expand the moral boundary created by

traditional practices for their selfish interest. The youths have built on the cultural acceptability of alcoholic and other psychoactive substances within the context of traditional rights to introduce other substances and increase number of traditional items which are to be collected or given to the youths during traditional rites.

Information gotten through interview revealed that the youths have seized the opportunity to make demands outside what was culturally accepted thereby shifting the acceptable boundaries and using such avenue to showcase deviant or anti-social behaviours under the influence of alcohol and drugs which were not morally prescribed by the elders. Alan (2003) gave credence to the findings when he argued that the main reason for alcohol and drug abuse may be psychological (to ease pain or discomfort, to reach euphoria, or to forget unpleasant reality) or sociological (peer pressure, the news media or substance-oriented society, status-seeking,), out of inquisitiveness, world-weariness, to ease fear, enhance sexual and other pleasures, or influence of family background. The findings of the study hereby revealed that community life among the people of Etinan Local Government Area is facing a serious shift from what was formerly known and considered to be driven by good cultural values to what is today seen as an anti-value or distorted value lifestyle by the youths due to the influence of psychoactive substances and drug abuse by some youths of the local government area. It was discovered that some youths have through the influence of psychoactive drug and alcohol abuse deviate from the socially accepted codes of conduct and practices.

On the formation of a cycle for alcohol and drug abuse among the Iman Ibom youths, gathered data revealed that Iman Ibom youths are conscious of the traditional practices as a cycle of abuse such that they make case for it during traditional events. It was gathered that Iman Ibom youths know the cycle by the youths will in traditional event work to enforce the cycle as part of the conventional practices of Iman Ibom people. Culture is learned, as the youths learned through the cycle of collecting youths items

(mkpomkparawa) as part of traditional practices in the culture of Iman Ibom people. They get acquainted with the cycle and the changes within the cycle which occur at the point of passage from the youth age cohort to that of the elder. These findings have credence from further findings of other researcher who proposed that cultural norms and traditional practices are forms of strong predictors of binge alcohol consumption and substance abuse (Usoro *et al.*, 2015, 2018; Peters, 2019, 2020^a, 2020^b, 2022, 2023 and Wilson *et al.*, 2020). Further findings shows that culture of alcohol and drug consumption among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area has brought about the creation of cycle of alcohol and drug abuse among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan. The traditional practices of traditional marriage ceremony, burial rites, ubud nkad, ukpok ndak, uno mkpo (collection of levy or traditional list), coronation of chiefs, village meetings, family meetings, consultations of village council, consultation of youths for political events and other cultural practices are the pattern of cycle of alcohol and drugs abuse among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.

Findings have revealed that “mkpomkparawa” has been a key factor and key player in the formation of cycle of alcohol and drug abuse among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. It was discovered that special allocated items to the youths are referred to as “*Mkpomkparawa*”. Mkpomkparawa has become a cycle for breeding alcohol abusers and drug addicts among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The roles of mkpomkparawa among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area ranges from creation of patterns and cycle of alcohol and drug abuse, cycle of addiction, traditional code for preservation of alcohol and drug abuse, transfer of alcohol and drug consumption and abuse from one generation to the other, medium of collection of alcohol and psychoactive substances, to cycle of family tradition of alcohol and drug abuse. These findings have credence from Usoro *et al.*, (2018) who posit that factors like arrival of a new born baby,

circumcision of the new born babies especially the male child after 8 days of birth and rite of passage of age grade forms cycle of legitimate alcohol consumption among the Anaang people of Nigeria.

On criminal behaviours as a result of alcohol and substance abuse, findings show that as the Iman Ibom youth continue in alcohol and substance abuse, they tend to engage in criminal behaviours under the influence of Alcohol and substance abuse. Findings also show that some youths used substance abuse as means of taking criminal advantage over others as in young boys using substance abuse to take criminal advantage over young girls for raping and sexual exploitations. Credence to this finding is gotten from US Department of Justice (2023) who posited that to explain the processes, impact and control of deviancy, the five forms of deviance must be considered which are: the delinquent, the drug addict, the homosexual, the mentally ill, and suicides which behaviours found to be related to influence of alcohol and substance abuse. Most of the youths used “mkpomkparawa” as means of abuse of substance and findings show that when such items are not given as suppose, the youths seize the opportunity to cause trouble for criminal behaviour like stealing and looting of people’s properties during traditional rites events. Findings further showed that youths who abuse alcohol and substances have high tendencies of involving in criminal behaviour like rape, stealing, theft, thuggery, assault and fighting among the age cohort.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

This study examined the culture of alcohol and drug abuse among the Iman Ibom youths of Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The researcher adopted exploratory research design. This research design has anthropological, investigative, and explanatory potentials to generate evidence based data that was used in examining and explaining substantial issues raised in the study. Bandura's Social Learning Theory and Hirschi's Social Bonding Theory were adopted for theoretical framework in the study. Four research objectives were adopted by the researcher from which four research questions were created for the study. It was a qualitative researcher in which qualitative data collection methodology was adopted with inter schedule as data collection instrument and data collected through interviews, participant observation, key informant interviews and some forms discussion. The findings of the study were analysed thematically in accordance to the four research questions in order to achieve the research objectives, using excerpts reports from the study participants.

Findings of the study shown that alcohol and substance abuse is rooted in the traditional rites of the Iman Ibom people in Akwa Ibom State. Alcohol and drug abuse is traditional among the Iman Ibom youths of Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State and it is culturally cultivated in the cultural tenets of their traditional practices. Cultural practices like traditional marriage ceremony and burial ceremony create avenue for psychoactive substance abuse among the Iman Ibom youths of Etinan Local Government Area. The youths have built on the cultural acceptability of alcoholic and other psychoactive substances within the context of traditional rights to introduce other substances and increase number of traditional items which are to be collected or given to

the youths during traditional rites. Emergence of the data also revealed that youths have seized the opportunity to make demands outside what was culturally accepted thereby shifting the acceptable moral boundaries and using such avenue to showcase deviant or anti-social behaviours especially under influence of drugs and alcohol which were not morally prescribed by the elders.

On the cycle of alcohol and drug abuse among the Iman Ibom youths, findings revealed that the Iman Ibom youths are conscious of the traditional practices as cycle of abuse such that they make case for it during traditional events. It was gathered that Iman Ibom youths have knowledge of the cycle by the youths will in traditional event work to enforce the cycle as part of the conventional practices of Iman Ibom people. Culture is learned, as the youths learned through the cycle of collecting youths items (mkpomkparawa) as part of traditional practices in the culture of Iman Ibom people.

Further findings have revealed that “mkpomkparawa” has been a key factor and key player in the formation of cycle of alcohol and drug abuse among the youths of Iman Ibom Clan in Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. It was discovered that special allocated items to the youths are referred to as “*Mkpomkparawa*”. It was found out that the roles of mkpomkparawa among the Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area ranges from creation of patterns and cycle of alcohol and drug abuse, cycle of addiction, traditional code for preservation of alcohol and drug abuse, transfer of alcohol and drug consumption and abuse from one generation to the other, medium of collection of alcohol and psychoactive substances, to cycle of family tradition of alcohol and drug abuse.

Emergence of findings of the study shown that Iman Ibom youth continue in alcohol and substance abuse, they tend to engage in criminal behaviours under the influence of Alcohol and substance abuse. Findings also show that some youths used substance abuse

as means of taking criminal advantage over others as in young boys using substance abuse to take criminal advantage of young girls for raping and sexual exploitation.

5.2 Conclusion

The major objective of this study was to examine the culture of alcohol and drug abuse among Iman Ibom youths in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Culture has a great influence on the life of the people of Iman Ibom people in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Culture is learned and Iman Ibom youths learn about alcohol and drug abuse through traditional practices like traditional marriage rites, and burial rites which include ubob-ndak, ukpok-ndak, etc. Iman Ibom youths indulge in anti-social and anti-moral behaviours under the influence of alcohol and drug abuse. They tend to go against the elders and the moral code of the people. These traditional practices create a cultural pot called “mkpomkparawa” (youths’ item). This mkpomkparawa contains alcohol, cigarettes, dry tobacco, beer, snuff, kai kai, and other psychoactive substances they now bring into the list like marijuana, and brew (a mixture of marijuana and kai kai). Mkpomkparawa has been a cycle of alcohol and drug abuse among the Iman Ibom youths. This cycle has been a traditional code and pattern through which alcohol and drug abuse is preserved and transfer from one generation to the other. Iman Ibom youths continue in alcohol and substance abuse as a cycle, they tend to engage in criminal behaviours under the influence of alcohol and psychoactive substance abuse. Some of the Iman Ibom youths used substance abuse as means of taking criminal advantage over others as in young boys using substance abuse to take criminal advantage over young girls for raping and sexual exploitations, robbery, burglary, thuggery, stealing, and other deviant behaviours.

5.3 Recommendations

The researcher made the following recommendations:

- i. Iman Ibom people should consider training their young ones on the moral values and moral codes of Iman Ibom customs and seek how to control alcohol and psychoactive substances consumption by the youths in order to control abuse.
- ii. Iman Ibom people should understand the cycle of alcohol and drug abuse created by the traditional practices of alcohol and psychoactive substances consumption and seek how to control such practices.
- iii. Mkpomkparawa as traditional items for the youths should be reconsidered for control of alcohol and drug abuse among the youths.
- iv. Parents should keep certain level of control of their children's engagement in alcohol and psychoactive substance consumption whether it is traditional right or not and control their engagement with peers with criminal tendencies.

5.4 Contribution to knowledge

The following are the contributions of this study to knowledge:

- i. Traditional practices among Iman Ibom people encourage alcohol and drug consumption which lead to abuse among youths.
- ii. Alcohol and drug are responsible for most of youth's distortion of moral values among Iman Ibom people.
- iii. Traditional practices are cycles of alcohol and drug consumption and abuse and this is passed from one generation to another.
- iv. Mkpomkparawa is a traditional pattern created for consumption and abuse of alcohol and drugs among Iman Ibom youths in Etinan Local Government Area.
- v. Alcohol and drugs consumptions are key factors to criminal activities by Iman Ibom youths in Etinan Local Government Area.

5.5 Suggestions for further studies

The researcher make the following suggestions for further researches:

- i. Impacts of Mkpomkparawa on the socio-economic status of families in Iman Ibom Clan, Etinan Local Government Area.
- ii. The roles of traditional practices on the wellbeing of Iman Ibom people.
- iii. Impacts of cycle of alcohol and drugs abuse among youths in Iman Ibom Clan, Southern Nigeria.
- iv. The roles of elders in the culture of alcohol and drugs abuse among Iman Ibom youths.

REFERENCES

- Abbott, P. and Chase, D. M. (2008). Culture and Substance Abuse: Impact of Culture Affects Approach to Treatment. *Journal of Substance Use and Misuse*. 25(1): 15 – 22.
- Abbott, P. and Chase, D. M. (2008). Culture and Substance Abuse: Impact of Culture Affects Approach to Treatment. Retrieved online on 17th January, 2024.
- Adetiloye, A. A. and Abel, O. A. (2022). Drug Abuse among Nigerian Youth and Its Consequences – A Review of Literature. *Sokoto Journal of Medical Laboratory Science* 7(2):101-108.
- Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development, Labour and Manpower Planning (2018). Akwa Ibom State Demographic Dividend Profile. Uyo.
- Alcohol Concern (2014). *Alcohol in the System: Report An examination of alcohol and youth offending in London*. The Prisoner Crime Reduction Survey. London. Retrieved on 23 January, 2024.
- Anderson, C. A. and Bushman, B. J. (2001). "Effects of violent video games on aggressive behavior, aggressive cognition, aggressive affect, physiological arousal, and pro-social behavior: A meta-analytic review of the scientific literature". *Psychological Science*, 12 (5): 353–359.
- Anonymous (2024). Young People and Risks of Alcohol. <https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/articles/young-people-and-risks-alcohol>
- Bandura, A. (1963). Social learning and personality development. New York: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston. 76-82.
- Bandura, A. (1971). "Social Learning Theory" (PDF). General Learning Corporation. Archived from the original (PDF) on 24 October 2013. Retrieved 25th January, 2024.
- Bandura, A. (2004). Social cognitive theory for personal and social change by enabling media. Retrieved from <http://web.stanford.edu/dept/psychology/bandura/pajares/Bandura2004Media.pdf> on 17th January, 2024
- Bryceson, D. F. 2002. *Alcohol in Africa: Mixing Business, Pleasure and Politics*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann, p. 3-21.
- Burgess, R., and Akers, R. (2011). A Differential Association-Reinforcement Theory of Criminal Behavior. *Social Problems*, 14, (2): 128-147
- Chomsky, N. (1995). "A review of B. F. Skinner's Verbal Behavior". *Journal of Languages*, 35 (1): 26– 58.
- Casey, S., Jones, O. and Somerville, J. (2011). Braking and accelerating of the adolescent brain. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*. 7(5): 64 – 78.

- Chersich, M. F. and Rees, H. V. (2010). Causal links between binge drinking patterns, unsafe sex and HIV in South Africa: its time to intervene". *International Journal of STD AIDS*. 21 (1): 2–7p.
- Chia, P. N., Awopetu, R. G., Ugese, J. I. and Apaa, T. (2015). Pattern of Psychoactive substance use among patients at the psychiatric unit of Federal Medical Centre, Makurdi. Presented at 2nd CRISA symposium on Drug Control and Drug Policy. 28th-29th October, 2015 @ Barcelona Hotels, Abuja.
- Ekpenyong, N. S. (2012). Drug Abuse in Nigerian Schools: A Study of Selected Secondary Institutions in Bayelsa State, South-South, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 5(3): 260-268.
- Enamhe, D. C. and Maxwell-Borjor, A. E. (2021). Nigeria Drug Abuse and the Nigerian Youth. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosiologi Dialektika Kontemporer* 8(1): 1-17.
- Esen, R. E. and Peters, M. I. (2023). Mental Illness and the Panacea of Orthodox Medicine Patronage Among Iman Ibom People of Southern Nigeria. *Global Journal of Communication and Humanities* (GJCH). Eleviv Publishing Group, USA. 2(1): 2 - 16.
- Fetterman, D. M. (2010). *Ethnography: Step-by-Step*. SAGE Publication, Inc. California. 42-50.
- Fuhrmann, D., Ravignani, A., Marshall-Pescini, S., and Whiten, A. (2014). "Synchrony and motor mimicking in chimpanzee observational learning". *Scientific Reports*. 4: 5283
- Garnett, C., Kastaun, S., Brown, J. and Kotz, D. (2022). Alcohol consumption and associations with sociodemographic and health-related characteristics in Germany: A population survey. *Addictive Behaviors*. 125(10): 59-71.
- Gavin, L. (2023). *Drinking Cultures around the World*. Retrieved online as PDF file on 23rd January, 2024).
- Gilbertson, R., Prather, R. and Nixon, S. J. (2008). The role of selected factors in the development and consequences of alcohol dependence. *Alcohol Research and Health*. 31(4):389-99.
- Gilligan, C., Kypri, K., Johnson, N., Lynagh, M. and Love, S. (2013). Parental supply of alcohol and adolescent risky drinking. *Drug and Alcohol Review*. 31(6):754–62.
- Grusec, J. (1992). "Social Learning Theory and developmental psychology: The legacies of Robert Sears and Albert Bandura". *Developmental Psychology*. 28 (5): 776–786.
- Hagler, A. (2024). *Alcohol Consumption and Levels of Violence*. Retrieved online as PDF file on 23rd January, 2024 from <https://www.mckendree.edu/academics/scholars/hagler-issue-28.pdf>

- Handren, L. M., Donaldson, C. D. and Crano, W. D. (2016). Adolescent Alcohol Use: Protective and Predictive Parent, Peer, and Self-Related Factors. *Prevention science: the Official Journal of the Society for Prevention Research*. 17(7):862 – 871.
- Heath, D. W. (2001). Cultures and substance abuse. *Psychiatrist Clinical Journal of North America*, 17 (24):479-496.
- Hollin, C. R. (2003). Young offenders and alcohol: a survey of the drinking behaviour of a Borstal population. *Journal of Adolescence Studies*. 6(2):161-74.
- <https://www.nidirect.gov.uk/articles/young-people-and-risks-alcohol>
- Hull, C. L. (1990). "Simple trial and error learning: A study in psychological theory". *Psychological Review*, 37(3): 241–256.
- Ibrahim, H. A., S Mahmud, S., Abubakar, A., Harazimi, A. C, and Abdulkadir, S. (2016). Effect of Drug Abuse Among Youth and Its Impact on Learning. *Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences (IOSR-JPBS)*. 11(1): 14 – 17.
- Lakhanpal, P. and Agnihotri, A., K. (2007). Drug Abuse an International Problem: A Short Review with Special Reference to African Continent. *Journal of Medicine and Toxicology*, 1(1), 1-11.
- Mason, W. A., Hitch, J. E., Kosterman, R., McCarty, C. A., Herrenkohl, T. I., and Hawkins, J. D. (2010). Growth in adolescent delinquency and alcohol use about young adult crime, alcohol use disorders, and risky sex: A comparison of youth from low-versus middle-income backgrounds. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, and Allied Disciplines*, 51(12), 1377-1383.
- Massawe, A. E., Ruheza, S., and Msambila, A. A. (2022). The Significance of Culture and Regulations on Alcohol Abuse among Youths in Rombo District Council.
- McGovern, P. (2009). *Uncorking the Past: The Quest for Wine, Beer, and Other Alcoholic Beverages*. Berkley (CA). 71-95.
- McMurrin, M. (2012). *Alcohol-Related Violence: Prevention and Treatment*. John Wiley and Sons. p. 37
- Miller, W. J. and Hunter, L. (1990). The Relationship between Socio-economic Status and Household Smoking Patterns in Canada. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 7 (5): 36-43.
- Modo, I. V. O. (2016) *Issues in Anthropology: An Introductory Textbook*. Issele-Uku, Cultural Research Publisher. 44-53.
- Murdoch, D., Phil, R. O. and Ross, D. (2000). Alcohol and crimes of violence: present issues. *International Journal of Addiction*. 25(9):1065-1081.

- Muthén, B. O. and Muthén, L. K. (2000). The development of heavy drinking and alcohol-related problems from ages 18 to 37 in a US national sample. *Journal of Studies on Alcohol*. 61:290–300.
- Myadze, T. I and Rwomire, A. (2014). Alcoholism in Africa during the Late Twentieth Century: A Socio-Cultural Perspective. *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 5(2); 1 – 9
- Nelson, B. (2017). Nevada's Driving Under the Influence (DUI) laws. *NVPAC*. Advisory Council for Prosecuting Attorneys. Retrieved online on 23rd January, 2024.
- Nelson, S. S. (2013). Germans Are Drinking Less Beer These Days, But Why?. *NPR*. Retrieved January 17th, 2024
- Neufeld, M. and Rehm, J. (2013). Alcohol Consumption and Mortality in Russia since 2000: Are there any Changes Following the Alcohol Policy Changes Starting in 2006. *Alcohol and Alcoholism*. 48(2): 222–230.
- Nwagu, E. N., Dibia, S. I. C. and Odo, A. N. (2017). Socio-cultural norms and roles in the use and abuse of alcohol among members of a rural community in Southeast Nigeria. *Health Education Research*, 32 (5): 423–436,
- Nwagu, E. N., Dibia, S. I. C. and Odo, A. N. (2017). Socio-cultural norms and roles in the use and abuse of alcohol among members of a rural community in Southeast Nigeria. *Health Education Research*, 32 (5): 423–436,
- Orford, J. (2005). Disabling the public interest: gambling strategies and policies for Britain. *Addiction*. 100 (9): 216-224.
- Osaki, H., Mshana, G., Mbata, D., Kapiga, S. and Changalucha, J. (2018). Social Space and Alcohol Use Initiation among Youth in Northern Tanzania. *PLoS One*. 7: (13)9
- Osei-Bonsu, ., Appiah, P. K., Norman, I. D., Asalu, G. A., Kweku, M. Ahiabor, S. Y., Takramah, W. K., Duut, A. A., Ntow, G. E. and Boadu. S. (2017). Prevalence of Alcohol Consumption and Factors Influencing Alcohol Use Among the Youth in Tokorni-Hohoe, Volta Region of Ghana. *Science Journal of Public Health*. 5(3): 205-214.
- Peters, M. I. (2019). Cultural Practices Enhancing Drug Abuse among Rural Youths in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. A Published Dissertation. *Researchgate*. 1- 119.
- Peters, M. I. and Basse, A. E. (2020). Psychoactive Drug Use and Drug Abuse among Young People in Riverine Areas of Nigeria: A Spotlight on Selected Communities in Akwa Ibom State. *Ripples of Culture: Journal of Anthropology*. Volume 1 Number, 1: 62 – 72.
- Peters, M. I., Basse, A. E. and Nya, A. (2020). Still Hoping for Medical prescribe Drugs: Unveiling the Experiences of Farmers in Farm Settlement Areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Perspectives on Drugs, Alcohol and Society in Africa. In: Abiyoko and Obot (Eds). A Publication of CRISA. Uyo.

- Peters, M. I., Basse, A. E., Usoro, N. A. and Samuel, M. E. (2022). Hymn No. 4: A Novel Psychoactive Substance Consumption among Iman Ibom Youths of the Niger Delta Region. *International Journal of Education and Science Development (IJESD)* 1(2): 13 – 19.
- Peters, M. I., Usoro, N. A., James, A. C., Emeh, P. B. and Oyebanji, A. O. (2023). Substance Abuse and Deviant Behaviours among Iman Ibom Youths: Latent Dysfunction of Selected Communities, pp50 – 58. In I. V. O. Modu, K. S. Mboho, E. R. Udoh and U. U. Effiong. *Academic Practitioners' Research for Sustainable Development Goals in Africa*. Published by International Centre for Integrated Development Research. Ikot Ekpene
- Peters, M. I., Usoro, N. A., Mboho, K. S., and Ononokpono, D. N. (2023). Culture Of Alcohol and Psychoactive Substance Abuse: A Qualitative Interrogation Of Distorted Values Among Iman Ibom Youths. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, 1(1), 93–113.
- Prichard, J and Payne, J. (2005). Alcohol, drugs and crime: a study of juveniles in detention. Australian Institute of Criminology, Research and Public Policy Series. Retrieved on 23rd January, 2024.
- Rear (2014). "Monkey brains wired to share". *Nature*. 506 (7489): 416–417.
- Richardson, A, and Budd T. (2003). Young adults, alcohol, crime and disorder. *Crime Behaviour and Mental Health Journal*. 13(1):5-16.
- Robert, F. M. (2018) Social Bond Theory. *The Sage Encyclopedia of Criminal Psychology*. Retrieved online on 23rd January, 2024.
- Roman, E. and Reid, R. (2012). Assessing the Relationship between Alcohol Outlets and Domestic Violence: Routine Activities and the Neighborhood Environment. *Violence and Victims*, 27 (5), 811-828.
- Room, R. (2013). *The Cultural Framing of Addiction*. Centre for Social Research on Alcohol and Drugs. Trivium Publications, Pittsburgh, PA. 34 – 50
- Schaik, C. P. V. and Burkart, J. M. (2011). "Social learning and evolution: the cultural intelligence hypothesis". *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*, 366(1567): 1008–1016.
- Stanley, L. R., Beauvais, F., Walker, P. S. and Walker, R. D. (2009). Initiation of Alcohol Use Among Urban American Indian Youth: A Discrete Time Hazards Model. *Journal of Ethnicity in Substance Abuse*. 8(4):359–77.
- Strycker, L. A., Duncan, S. C. and Pickering, M. A. (2003). The Social Context of Alcohol Initiation Among African American and White Youth. *Journal of Ethnicity in Substance Abuse*. 2(1):35–42.
- Sung, H. (2016), Alcohol and Crime. *The Blackwell Encyclopedia of Sociology*, American Cancer Society, pp. 1–2,

- Taylor and Carroll (2001). *Youth Alcohol Consumption: Experiences and Expectations*. Ed. in P. Williams, *Alcohol, Young Persons and Violence*. Australian Institute of Criminology. Elect Printing, Canberra
- Tiruneh, B. T., Dachew, B. A. and Bifftu, B. B. (2015). Alcohol Use Related Injury in Northwest Ethiopia: A Cross-sectional Study. *African Journal of Drug and Alcohol Studies*, 14(1): 13 – 21.
- Uddin, L. Q.; Iacoboni, M.; Lange, C.; Keenan, J. P. (2007). "The self and social cognition: the role of cortical mid line structures and mirror neurons". *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 11 (4): 153–157.
- Udoh, E. A., Okediji, E. A., Umoh, O. O. and Usoro, N. A. (2016). Drug Use And Dating Violence Among University Undergraduates. In I. S. Obot and G. E. Abikoye. *Perspectives on Drugs, Alcohol and Society in Africa*, CRISA, Uyo.
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2007). Drug Abuse and Drug Dependence Treatment Situation, in Nigeria. According to UNODC data for the year 2007. Available at http://www.unodc.org/docs/treatment/CoPro/Web_Nigeria.pdf
- Usoro, N. A., Okediji, E. A., Udoh, E. A. and Ineme, M. E. (2017). Prevalence Of Drug Use Among Internally Displaced Persons In Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. In I. S. Obot and G. E. Abikoye *Perspectives on Drugs, Alcohol and Society in Africa*, CRISA, Uyo.
- Usoro, N. A., Ononkpono, D. N., Ursula, E. and Nkereuwem, N. J. (2015). Community Perspectives on Cultural Practices and Belief Systems Influencing Alcohol and Drug: A Qualitative Study in Anaang Community, Nigeria. *African Journal of Drug and Alcohol Studies*, 14(1): 146 – 160.
- Usoro, N. A. and Ekong, I. C. (2016). The Place of Cultural Practices and Symbol Forms among Annang People of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *South-South Journal of Culture and Development*. 18(1)166-189
- Usoro, N. A., Enwongo, A. O., Emeh, A. U. and Mfon E. I. (2017). Prevalence of Drug Use among Internally Displaced Persons in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. In: Abikoye, G. A. and Isidore, S. O. (ed) *Perspectives on Drugs, Alcohol and Society in Africa*. A Publication of CRISA.
- Whiten, A., McGuigan, N., Marshall-Pescini, S. and Hopper, L. M. (2009). "Emulation, imitation, over-imitation and the scope of culture for child and chimpanzee". *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*, 364 (1528): 2417 – 2428.
- Wickert, C. (2022). Social Bonds Theory (Hirschi). *Zuletzt Aktualisiert*. Retrieved on 23rd January, 2024 from <https://soztheo.de/theories-of-crime/control/social-bonds-theory-hirschi/?lang=en>
- Williams, P. (2001). *Alcohol, Young Persons and Violence*. Australian Institute of Criminology. Elect Printing, Canberra

- Willis, J. (2011). "Beer Used to Belong to Older Men": Drink and Authority among the Nyakyusa of Tanzania. *Africa*. 71(3):373–390.
- Wilson, N. U., Usoroh, R. O. and Peters, M. I. (2020). Unorthodox Use of Orthodox Drugs Use among Rural Women in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Perspectives on Drugs, Alcohol and Society in Africa*. In: Abiyoke and Obot (Eds). A Publication of CRISA. Uyo. 5 (2020).
- Yusuf, U. L., Gazali, W. A. and Abdullahi, M. (2014). Drug Abuse among Youths in Nigeria: Implications to National Development. Retrieved online on the 23rd January, 2024.
- Zapolski, T.C.B., Fisher, S., Banks, D., Hensel, D., and Barnes-Najor, J. (2017). Examining the protective effect of ethnic identity on drug attitudes and use among a diverse youth population. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 46(8), 1702-1715. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10964-016-0605-0>

LIST OF MY EXPECTED PUBLICATIONS

1. Cultural Response to Alcohol and Drug Use: A Qualitative Interrogation of Distorted Values among Ibibio Youths.
2. Substance Abuse and Deviant Behaviours among Ibibio Youths: An Anthropological Interrogation of Some Ibibio Traditional Rites.
3. Mkpomkparawa: A Traditional Cycle of Alcohol and Drug Abuse among Iman Ibom Youths.
4. Alcohol and Drug Abuse: Power for Distorted Values among Youths in Etinan Local Government Area.

APPENDIX I: TRANSMITTAL LETTER

Department of Sociology and Anthropology
Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Uyo, Uyo
Akwa Ibom State
May, 2024

Dear Study participant,

I am Moses Idongesit Peters, a PhD student of the Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Faculty of Social Sciences in the University of Uyo. I am conducting a research on the topic “**An Assessment of Culture of Alcohol and Drug Abuse among Iman Ibom Youths**“

I would greatly appreciate if you could give me your time for a brief interview to assist me in executing this study. The information sought from you is solely for academic purpose and will be kept strictly confidential.

Yours faithfully,

Thank you

Moses Idongesit PETERS

(20/PG/SS/SA/PHD/008)

APPENDIX II

DEPARTMENT OF SOCIOLOGY AND ANTHROPOLOGY

UNIVERSITY OF UYO

INTERVIEW SCHEDULE

This interview schedule is for data collection on the **AN ASSESSMENT OF CULTURE OF ALCOHOL AND DRUG ABUSE AMONG IMAN IBOM YOUTHS**. Your honest opinion will be treated with high anonymity and confidentiality.

Thank You.

SECTION A

Sex

Male: Female:

Age:

15 – 19 20 - 24 25– 29 30 – 34 35 – 40 41 – 45 46 -50

Marital Status:

Single Married Divorced Separated
Widowed Cohabiting

Highest Educational Qualification:

No Formal Education Primary Education
Post Primary Education Tertiary Education

Religious Affiliation:

Catholic Protestant Pentecostal Islam

Traditional Religion Others (Specify) _____

SECTION B

Do you have a good knowledge of the cultural practices of the people of Etinan Local Government Area?

Does your culture accept the use of alcohol and illicit substances like cigarettes?

If yes, on what ground is the cultural acceptability rooted?

Do you know cultural practices that permit alcohol consumption and other drug substances for youths in Etinan Local Government Area?

If yes, what cultural practices permit such?

Have you attended or participated in any of such practices in your family or community in Etinan Local Government Area before?

If yes, what types of alcohol drinks and drug related substances do they permit or give to youths in your family and community?

Do youths consume these alcohol drinks and the drugs substances provided for them?

Do the youths have access to any other type of alcohol and drugs substances during cultural event?

If yes, what are the types?

How do youths behave when they have finish taking or while taking alcohol and other drugs substances/

What are the observed attitudes of the youths under the influence of alcohol and drugs?

Do you have any knowledge about youths' items (mkpo-mkparawa) as a cultural practice in Etinan local Government Area?

If yes, do the youths' items contain alcohol and items that are drug related?

If yes, what are the items?

Do youths item a cultural regular thing?

If yes, do you belief that youth item (mkpo-mkparawa) enhance alcohol and drug abuse among youths in Etinan Local Government area?

If yes, how?

Did those elders who take alcohol and other drug substances participated in consuming same things as youth items when they were youths?

If yes, please can you illustrate or site any example you know?

Do you see that those who participate in youth items tend to continue in addiction as they grow into elders?

It yes, can you give illustration or example of any?

Do you agree that the culture provide cycle of alcohol and drugs use, abuse and addiction from youths to elders?

If yes, can you give an observation or illustration?

Do you believe that alcohol and drug abuse influence criminal behaviour among youths in Etinan Local Government Area?

If yes, have you had any witness or been a victim of such an act before?

What are your observable experiences of the influence of alcohol and drug abuse on youth engagement in crimes and violence? ,.....

What are the types of crimes that youths engage in under the influence of alcohol and drugs?

Have you seen some of them in trouble with the police because of alcohol or drugs.....

What do you think, makes the youths addicted to excessive alcohol and drugs?
.....

How do you think the youth can be controlled when it comes to taking alcohol?
.....

How do you think the youth can stop taking these psychoactive substances?
.....

What do you think the government should do to regulate alcohol and drug use by the youth?

Thank you!

APPENDIX III

PICTORAL PAGES FOR ETHNOGRAPHIC PHOTOGRAPHS

An elder taking a combination of Palmwine and beer with youth. Source: Peters (2023)

Elders with youths at a traditional function where beer, palmwine, kaikai, hot drinks are presented. Source: Peters (2024)

Researcher at Ubug Ndak traditional burial rite where Palm wine, hot drink, kaikai, beer, cigarettes, and snuff were presented to elders and youths. Source: Peters (2024)

Researcher at a Ubub Ndak traditional burial rite where Palm wine, hot drink, kaikai, beer, cigarettes, and snuff were presented to elders and youths. Source: Peters (2024)

Youths clear venue for the Traditional marriage rite while the elders wait with the Mkpo ndito ete items that are made up of beer, palm wine, kai kai, hot drink, cigarettes, snuffs, dry tobacco leaves, kola nut, and penetrol. Source: Peters (2024)

Youth President/Obong Efak addressed youths who were making demands for Marijuana and Cigarettes to be added to the provided 20 litres of palm wine, 2 cartons of beer, 2 creates of minerals, 1 bottle of Hot drink, 1 bottle of Kaikai, 1 full stick of fish, food and meat for Ubub Ndak (Building of Traditional Tent). Source: Peters 2024

The brew which is a combination of marijuana, kaikai, and a little cocaine, is a regular drink now at every traditional event.

Source: Peters (2024)

A traditional function whereby psychoactive items were presented to the elders and the youths

Source: Peters (2024)

Alcohol and other psychoactive substances presented to the elder and youths as a traditional event.

Source: Peters (2019)